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CARPOS

Coachable Robot for Fruit Picking Operations

D4- Control schemes for occlusion-free active perception

Abstract:

The present document is a deliverable of the CARPOS project. It reports on Control schemes for occlusion-free active perception. In particular, the CARPOS team developed a number of control schemes for the active perception of the scene and mainly of the human activity, aiming towards capturing the task performed by the human through visual means. The need of actively observing the human activity sources from the non-homogeneous and relatively large uncertainty involved in most RGB-D cameras, especially along the “depth” direction, as well as possible occlusions within the scene. The control schemes developed by the CARPOS research team can be divided in two categories, each one of which is working on a different phase of the overall system, namely: a) Methods for finding the optimal pose of the moving camera for observing and detecting the exact location of the points of interest during the grasping of the fruit by the human (this is required at the start of the task demonstration) and b) Control schemes for incrementally learning the task from iterative visual observations of the human action (this is required during the actual task demonstration by the human). The developed methods were published in four (4) papers, the pre-print versions of which are attached to the end of this document.

Περίληψη στα Ελληνικά:

Το παρόν έγγραφο αποτελεί παραδοτέο του έργου CARPOS. Αναφέρεται σε σχήματα ελέγχου για ενεργό αντίληψη χωρίς αποκρύψεις. Συγκεκριμένα, η ομάδα του έργου CARPOS ανέπτυξε μια σειρά από σχήματα ελέγχου για την ενεργό αντίληψη της σκηνής και κυρίως της ανθρώπινης δραστηριότητας, με στόχο την καταγραφή της εργασίας που εκτελείται από τον άνθρωπο, μέσω οπτικών μέσων. Η ανάγκη για χρήση ενεργούς παρατήρησης πηγάζει από την ανομοιογενή και σχετικά μεγάλη αβεβαιότητα που εμπλέκεται στις περισσότερες κάμερες RGB-D, ειδικά κατά μήκος της κατεύθυνσης του "βάθους", καθώς και πιθανές αποκρύψεις του οπικού πεδίου εντός της σκηνής. Τα σχήματα ελέγχου που αναπτύχθηκαν από την ερευνητική ομάδα του έργου CARPOS μπορούν να χωριστούν σε δύο κατηγορίες, καθεμία από τις οποίες εργάζεται σε διαφορετική φάση του συνολικού συστήματος, δηλαδή: α) Μέθοδοι για την εύρεση της βέλτιστης στάσης της κινούμενης κάμερας για την παρατήρηση και ανίχνευση της ακριβούς θέσης των σημείων ενδιαφέροντος κατά την συγκράτηση των φρούτων από τον άνθρωπο (αυτό απαιτείται στην αρχή της επίδειξης της εργασίας) και β) Σχήματα ελέγχου για σταδιακή εκμάθηση της εργασίας από επαναληπτικές οπτικές παρατηρήσεις της ανθρώπινης δράσης (αυτό απαιτείται κατά την επίδειξη της εργασίας από τον άνθρωπο). Οι μέθοδοι που αναπτύχθηκαν δημοσιεύθηκαν σε τέσσερις (4) εργασίες, οι προ-δημοσιευμένες εκδόσεις των οποίων επισυνάπτονται στο τέλος αυτού του εγγράφου.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The goal of CARPOS project is to develop a system that captures and encodes the long-life experience of the farmers regarding the detachment of fruits from the plant without a cutting tool (also known as “fruit picking”). Inspired by the way the humans would transfer such a knowledge among them, i.e. when an experience farmer teaches a task to a novice one during her/his initiation to the profession, CARPOS aims at addressing this by utilizing multiple modalities, which have to be intuitive for the human-teacher. One of the first actions that an experienced farmer would do, towards this direction, is to firstly show (demonstrate) the task to the learner in front of her/his eyes. Therefore, the initial teaching phase of the CARPOS system, is considered to be the visual observation of the task when performed by the human-teacher (i.e. experienced farmer). Similarly to human-human teaching, this phase could involve multiple demonstration iterations, until a sufficient skill transfer is achieved.

Figure 1-The human learner intuitively adapts her/his pose of the head and eyes in order to optimally perceive the scene without occlusions.

During human-human teaching by demonstration (showing the action), the learner is rarely a passive observer, as she/he has to track the motion of the human hand, ensuring that the activity is not occluded by any obstacle and that the uncertainty of the observed action is minimized (an example is depicted in Fig. 1). This activity of the learner becomes even more evident and necessary when the action is demonstrated in unstructured and cluttered agricultural setups. Inspired by this curiosity-driven action of the human, the notion of “Active Perception” was introduced in Robotics and Machine-vision, which is in the core of WP2 of CARPOS project.

The two main characteristics of the fruit detachment action, in every crop type, are:

- a) The way the human has initially **grasped the fruit**, as this is crucial for the exertion of forces during the detachment motion. In most of the cases the grasp is not changed during the motion of the human hand for the detachment (Fig. 2a).
- b) The **spatial and temporal characteristics of the motion**, i.e. the exact trajectory/pattern of the human hand during the detachment. In particular, it is important to capture both the position and the orientation of the human hand during its action (Fig. 2b).

a) Capturing grasping pose

b) Capturing the detachment motion

Figure 2- Active visual observation of the fruit picking action.

Given the two aforementioned characteristics of the detachment skill, and assuming **an active sensor with the ability to move in Cartesian space**, the development of CARPOS project focused on two types of methods, namely the methods for selecting the optimal Next Best View (NBV) for maximizing the information gain regarding the grasping of the fruit by the human hand and the control schemes for optimally and actively perceiving the human hand motion during the detachment motion. **The developed methods, which are detailed in the papers provided in Appendix A**, are the following:

- **GRAsPAD**: Generalized framework for optimal grasp key-points active detection. *(Accepted at the 34th IEEE International Conference on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (IEEE RO-MAN), Eindhoven, The Netherlands)*
- **ActIVO**: An Active perception framework for skill transfer through Iterative Visual Observations *(Presented and included in the proceedings of the 32nd Mediterranean Conference on Control and Automation (IEEE MED), Chania, Greece)*
- Optimized UKF-based perception of a repetitive dynamic event *(Presented and included in the proceeding of the 23rd European Control Conference (ECC) in Thessaloniki, Greece)*
- **LAIF**: Learning by demonstration through Active Incremental data Fusion of task observations *(Accepted at the 2025 IEEE International Conference on Imaging Systems and Techniques (IEEE IST 2025), Strasbourg, France)*

2. STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE AND CONNECTION WITH OTHER DELIVERABLES OF THE PROJECT

The aforementioned proposed methods for tackling the problem of active perception for both optimally detecting the grasp key-points and capturing the human activity during the demonstrations **are presented and evaluated in detail in the papers included in Appendix A**. In the following Chapters a brief overview of the proposed methods is provided, highlighting the differences among them, as well as their performance.

The methods developed in this deliverable are integrated within the overall CARPOS system for optimally observing the human activity. The CARPOS platform incorporates an RGB-D camera **attached to its end-effector, i.e. an eye-in-hand camera**. One of the functionalities provided by the integrated system, is the “Visual Observation” of the activity of the human, which aims towards Learning by Demonstration through visual observation. The first time this functionality is initiated by the user, the system actively seeks for the best pose of the camera in order to optimally perceive the grasp key-points. This is achieved by the GRASPAD method, detailed in this deliverable. When this functionality is again triggered by the user, the systems seeks for the next best view for optimally perceiving and incrementally learning the action performed by the human. To this aim, the LAIF controller is employed, which constitutes essentially the final version of the controllers detailed in this deliverable for occlusion-free active perception of the human activity. Due to these facts, the deliverable is closely related to “D8 – System integration and Testing” and “D6 – Graphical human-machine interface and skill extraction through proprioceptive data”.

After learning the task through the active visual observation methods proposed in this deliverable, the system provides the user with the functionality of kinesthetically inspecting and correcting the task. In this, functionality, which is detailed in “D5 – Controller for unintentional and intentional pHRI during the coaching and autonomous operation”, the uncertainty of the visual training plays a crucial role to facilitate the kinesthetic correction along the axes with the highest uncertainty.

3. OPTIMAL GRASPING KEY-POINT DETECTION (GRASPAD)

Here, only a brief overview of the method is provided, as the method is detailed in the attached paper in Appendix A.1 (GRASPAD: Generalized framework for optimal grasp key-points active detection.)

One of the key challenges in robotics is grasping things in unstructured situations, especially for applications like agricultural harvesting. Consider a grasping scenario, such as picking a tomato fruit from a plant. The robot needs to initially identify the most efficient grasping position while accounting for occlusions, varying illumination, and the inherent diversity in the fruit’s shape and orientation, in order to carry out this task effectively.

In the context of Learning by Demonstration (LbD), we consider the case in which the human, who grasps the object, is instructed to keep her/his hand still in order for the system to acquire enough data for detecting the grasp pose. Furthermore, we consider the availability of a moving/actuated sensor, such as an RGB-D camera mounted on the robot’s end-effector, to improve perception skills. This sensor can actively change its position and orientation within 3D space, balancing exploration and exploitation tactics to improve its perspective, in contrast to

static perception systems. A conceptual diagram of the considered problem is provided in Fig. 3. We consider the case in which the human is instructed to keep her/his hand still for the process, involving her/him in the active perception loop. As it is important for the human not to shoulder too much physical or cognitive load, the systems aims not only at providing accurate estimates of the features, but also at being fast for facilitating the human involvement and ensuring her/his comfort.

The developed method's scientific contributions are the following:

- The method optimizes the sensor pose (which is considered to be attached to a mechanism), allowing rapid adjustment of the sensor viewpoint to improve grasp comprehension.
- To minimize the human partner's physical and mental burden during the process, a clear balance between accuracy and efficiency is sought.

We consider the availability of a trajectory planner and a trajectory tracking controller that are able to move the end-effector (with the camera) from its current pose, to a target pose $\mathbf{c}_p^* \in \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{S}^3$ (position in Cartesian coordinates and orientation in unit quaternion). One such option, which is employed in our case, is the utilization of a 5th order polynomial as the trajectory planner and the Closed Loop Inverse Kinematics algorithm (CLIK) for accurately tracking the trajectory generated (for the orientation the logarithmic error is employed in the CLIK algorithm), as we consider a robot driven by joint velocity commands. The motion of the robot is considered to be confined within a subset of $\mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{S}^3$, e.g. the robot's work-space, parameterized by $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^M$. For instance, if a sphere around a rough estimate of the center of the scene is considered to represent the allowable workspace of the end-effector, the polar coordinates can be utilized and therefore $\xi \triangleq [\varphi \ \theta]^T \in \mathcal{T}$, with $\mathcal{T} \subset \mathbb{R}^M$ the allowable subspace of the parameters defining the work-space of the robot. In other words, $\mathbf{c}_p^* \triangleq \mathbf{c}_p(\xi^*)$, with $\xi^* \in \mathcal{T}$ being the target parameters. Let us highlight that it is crucial that the trajectory generation mechanism should yield a trajectory which satisfies this constraint for all $t > 0$. For tackling the considered problem, we combine linear Kalman filtering for estimating the state of the perceived key-points, with the Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy (CMA-ES) algorithm for efficient and fast exploration of the pose/task space of the sensor, as shown in Fig. 4. Given the above rationale, the problem can be written, in a more mathematically rigorous form, as follows:

$$\xi^* = \arg \max_{\xi \in \mathcal{T}} J(\xi)$$

where $J(\xi) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ a reward function that reflects the information gain. More details can be found in the paper attached in Appendix A.1.

Figure 3 - The GRASPAD objective and concept solution

Figure 4 - Block diagram of the propose method.

Experimental evaluation of the GRAsPAD framework

For the experimental evaluation, the UR5e robotic manipulator is utilized with an eye-in-hand Realsense D435 RGB-D camera, as depicted in Fig.5. The proposed framework is implemented in Python and it is publicly available in this link:<https://github.com/CSRL-HMU/GRAsPAD>. For integrating the CMA-ES algorithm, which is in the core of the developed method, within our framework, the "cmaes" Python library is utilized. From this library the CMAwM (CMA-ES with margin) algorithm is employed, in order to ensure that the algorithm will be able to also handle cases in which the reward function exhibits a plateau, i.e. when its gradient of the reward is zero within a relatively large area

Figure 5 - Experimental setup with a mockup hand and tomato for extensive evaluation

For evaluating the framework, two experimental scenarios are considered:

1. The active detection of a grasp using a mock up setup with a plastic fruit and a realistic plastic human hand, **for extensive evaluation** and comparison
2. The active detection of a real human grasping case, involving a real tomato for testing the performance of the method in different light conditions and possible occlusion.

The outcomes of the experimental evaluation, which are detailed in the paper provided in Appendix A.1, not only fulfills the objective to find the optimal observation pose, but also exhibits fast convergence to the solution, which is a crucial requirement due to the human being in-the-loop. In order to improve the generalizability and robustness of the method, future work will concentrate on expanding the framework's capabilities to dynamic environments with moving objects and human operators, incorporating active perception strategies, and validating the method across a larger range of tasks and robotic platforms. Some representative results of the yielded images taken from the final found optimal pose are the ones depicted in Fig. 6a and b, considering an occlusion-free scenario and a scene with occlusions (tomato plant leaves) respectively. **Let us highlight that the initial view of the in-hand camera, in each one of these cases, did not include the tomato and/or the human hand, i.e. the view only included a flat wall.**

Figure 6 - Key-points detections and camera view from the optimally found pose by GRAsPAD (*The initial view did not include any key-point*)

4. ACTIVE PERCEPTION FOR OPTIMAL LEARNING FROM VISUAL OBSERVATIONS (METHODS: ACTIVO, OPTIMIZED UKF AND LAIF)

To achieve learning by demonstration of the fruit picking task through visual observations, in CARPOS we consider the case in which the motion of the frame of the human hand (e.g. a frame attached to the wrist of the human) is taught to the robot through iterative visual observations of demonstrations performed by the human-teacher. The action is observed using a moving **in-hand camera**, i.e. a camera attached to the end-effector of the robot. Given the uncertainty involved in the 3D-position estimate provided by the visual sensor, we aim at iteratively minimizing the uncertainty of the gathered information related to the motion executed by the tips of the human fingers. Gathering the maximum information, and consequently minimizing the uncertainty related to the trajectory followed by the human-hand, plays a crucial role on the learning performance and could significantly reduce the number of iterations required for skill transfer.

To tackle the aforementioned problem, CARPOS research team incrementally developed three control schemes, which are provided in Appendix A.2-4. These control schemes are briefly presented in the section below, while for more details the reader is advised to see the corresponding paper in the Appendix A.

4.1 ActIVO: An Active perception framework for skill transfer through Iterative Visual Observations

Here, only a brief overview of the method is provided, as the method is detailed in the attached paper in Appendix A.2.

Our initial approach was **ActIVO** framework (Active perception for skill transfer through Iterative Visual Observations). The concept of this framework is to estimate the position of a moving human fingertip for enabling LbD, following an iterative procedure, in which the total uncertainty of the estimated position of the hand is minimized in each iteration. In order to achieve this, a covariance weighted least square estimator based on multiple demonstrations of the same task and also an active perception control policy that moves the camera on-line, such that the uncertainty of the total captured

Figure 7 - The ActIVO rationale

data was minimized, were developed.

Regarding the proposed control scheme for the active sensor, the core idea was not only to minimize the observation uncertainty along the axis with the maximum total uncertainty but also to keep the hand frame at the center of field of view of the active sensor. The rationale of the ActIVO control scheme is to complementary (in each iteration) gather information about the direction with the highest current uncertainty. To achieve this, in each iteration, the axis of the camera with the lowest uncertainty is aligned with the axis of the highest uncertainty of the already observed motion. This concept solution is depicted in Fig. 7, with the ellipsoids representing the uncertainty of the sensor and that of the current knowledge of the task. By using the covariance weighted least square estimator we are able to reconstruct the demonstrated motion from multiple visual observations.

Experimental evaluation of the ActIVO framework

The proposed framework was evaluated experimentally utilizing a UR5e robotic manipulator with an Intel RealSense D415 RGB-D camera attached to its end-effector. For the kinematics of the robot, the Python version of the Robotics toolbox¹ was utilized. The frame rate of the camera was set to 30 fps and the control cycle of the robot was set to 2 ms. For the human hand detection and localization, the “Mediapipe Hands” algorithm² was employed, pretrained with a sample of 16,000 real and 100,000 artificially generated human hand images. The hand detection algorithm and the control loop were running on different threads to ensure that the timing of the control loop remained unaffected.

¹ P. Corke and J. Haviland, “Not your grandmother’s toolbox—the robotics toolbox reinvented for python,” in IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Autom. (ICRA), 2021, pp. 11 357–11 363

² A. Vakunov, C.-L. Chang, F. Zhang, G. Sung, M. Grundmann, and V. Bazarevsky, “Mediapipe hands: On-device real-time hand tracking,” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://mixedreality.cs.cornell.edu/workshop>

For evaluating the framework, two experiments were conducted, the first considering a simple path of pre-determined geometry on a flat surface, and the second considering a fruit picking operation. In each iteration, an audio cue, signifying the initiation of the demonstration, was provided to the human, triggered as soon as the human hand was perceived by the camera. The camera's initial pose for each iteration was selected to be roughly orthogonal to the previous view-point of the camera. To synchronize signals across iterations, we identified the closest point on the trajectory of the first iteration (considered the reference trajectory) to the current position of the robot, within a window of 500 samples ahead in time. For facilitating this procedure a first order low-pass IIR filter with a cutoff frequency of 5 rad/s was applied to the reference trajectory.

Figure 8 - Experimental evaluation of the ActIVO framework

The results of the experimental evaluation, which are provided in detail in the paper of Appendix A.2, clearly demonstrate the improved motion reconstruction performance attained by utilizing ActIVO, as compared to a single-shot reconstruction or a non-weighted pseudo-inverse estimation.

In Fig. 9, one of the experiments are presented, in which the trajectory reconstruction with the proposed method (yellow line) is shown, as compared to a single demonstration (blue line) or even after taking the simple average in each time instance (black dotted line). A notable spike in the perceived position is evident in the first iteration (blue line) around $t \approx 1.2s$, primarily attributed to an error in the camera's depth estimation. It is important to highlight that relying solely on a single observation from one viewpoint, such as that of the first iteration, would result in significantly erroneous thumb position estimates, potentially exhibiting high rates or even discontinuities. However, the proposed method effectively eliminates this spike by taking into

Figure 9 - Estimated trajectories of the human hand

account data from the second iteration and considering the non-homogeneous uncertainty of the sensor in the estimation process, in particular the fact that the error predominantly occurs along the z-axis of the camera during the first iteration. Indeed, the dotted line in Fig. 9 depicts the estimated trajectory without axis weighting based on covariance, i.e. by simply computing the mean of the perceived trajectories. It is worth noting how this approach is influenced by the spike at $t \approx 1.2s$.

4.2 Optimized UKF-based perception of a repetitive dynamic event

Here, only a brief overview of the method is provided, as the method is detailed in the attached paper in Appendix A.3.

In the ActIVO framework, the camera was allowed to move in **real time** to find the optimal observation pose (on-line pose optimization). This means that during the demonstration performed by the human, the robotic system is moving, simultaneously with the human action, in order to find the optimal view pose. Despite the use of Collaborative robots (known as Cobots), which generally take into serious consideration safeties in the context of human and robot interaction/collaboration, having moving sensors may lead to trust issues. So, in order to be able to interact with farmers that have lower collaboration confidence with robots, an Optimized UKF-based perception method for repetitive dynamic events (such as fruit detachment demonstrations), was developed. The proposed method is detailed in Appendix A.3. The developed method is based on an off-line optimization procedure to auto-determine the optimal sensor's pose and at the same time to auto-tune an observer.

Figure 10 - The concept of Optimized UKF-based perception

In particular, the developed method, considering an active sensor, seeks for the optimal parameters and Next Best View, in order to minimize the uncertainty involved in the perception and estimation of the state of an RDE during its next occurrence (if natural) or execution (if artificial). The method builds upon the ActIVO framework. The advancements of this work, as compared to the previous work, are the following:

- The Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) is utilized for estimating the observed state of the system, which ensures optimal data fusion, as opposed to ActIVO in a weighted mean was utilized.
- The optimization problem is solved before the repetition of the event, i.e. we seek for the global overall optimum sensor pose and UKF parameters through simulations, as compared to ActIVO in which the problem was solved in real-time, yielding a near-optimal (sub-optimal) solution.

To achieve the aforementioned advancements, the CARPOS research team employ the notion of Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF)³, which does not involve the analytic computation of the Jacobian of the system, at the expense of introducing a number of parameters that needs to be tuned. Given the difficulty involved in the tuning of the parameters and the fact that the uncertainty is considered to be a function of the pose of the sensor, the contribution of the proposed solution is that it automatically seeks the optimal parameters of the UKF, as well as the optimal pose of the sensor, in order to minimize the total uncertainty of the estimate that will be provided by the UKF during the next repetition of the event. Note that the pose of the sensor is considered to be static during a single repetition of the event.

Experimental evaluation of the Optimized UKF-based active perception method

For validating the proposed method, in addition to extensive simulation studies, we conducted experiments using a ZED 2 RGB-D camera, attached to the tip of a UR10e robot, as shown in Fig. 11. A video recording of the experiments can be found in the following link:

<https://youtube.com/shorts/jwgLR7wDzdg>. The task involves the estimation of the state (position and velocity) of a swinging pole, i.e. a pendulum. For detecting the tip of the pole a predetermined April-tag (<https://github.com/AprilRobotics/apriltag>) is utilized, as the detection of specific characteristics/features is outside of the

focus of the paper. As the center of the scene (i.e. the center of the sphere of allowable poses), an arbitrary point is selected, close to the pendulum's evolution, while the allowable sphere is selected to have a predefined radius, being within the range in which ZED 2 can provide a depth estimate. The pivot point, as well as the exact length of the pole are considered to be parameters of the already modelled dynamical system that are however characterized by an uncertainty.

Note that although the experiments were not performed using a human subject, extending the method to consider and incorporate the human hand detection instead of the AprilTag is straight forward,

Figure 11 - Experiment using UR10e and ZED 2 as an eye-in-hand.

Figure 12 - Results of the estimated trajectory of the tip, from the optimized pose (left) and from the non-optimized one (right). Experimental validation of the proposed Optimied UKF-based method

³ E. Wan and R. Van Der Merwe, "The unscented kalman filter for nonlinear estimation," in Proceedings of the IEEE 2000 Adaptive Systems for Signal Processing, Communications, and Control Symposium (Cat. No.00EX373), 2000, pp. 153–158.

while the modelling essentially constitutes the encoding of the human behavior via a Dynamic System, e.g. a Dynamic Movement Primitives model, as the one employed in our project.

The results of the evaluation procedure, which are detailed in the paper attached in Appendix A.3, show a convergence in finding best observation poses and improvement in optimal target key points estimation, at each iteration. In Fig. 12, a representative example of predicting the pendulum motion from the optimal pose found by the method (left) and the non-optimized pose (right). Notice the significant erroneous pattern occurred when the motion is observed from the non-optimized pose, in contrast to the one achieved from the optimally found one.

4.3 LAIF: Learning by demonstration through Active Incremental data Fusion of task observations

Here, only a brief overview of the method is provided, as the method is detailed in the attached paper in Appendix A.4.

The final control scheme developed in the CARPOS project for tackling the problem of active perception of the human activity, in the, builds upon the aforementioned ActIVO framework, in order to make it more robust and also address the presence of occlusions within the scene. The control scheme is coined as LAIF (LAIF: Learning by demonstration through Active Incremental data Fusion of task observations) and the related paper can be found in Appendix A.4. The proposed framework considers an active observer, which acts so as to maximize the information gathered towards the modelling of the observed motion. In the core of the method, a Kalman-filter inspired data fusion mechanism is employed, that incorporates a Dynamic Movement Primitives model. The proposed method is **proven theoretically and experimentally**, to minimize the uncertainty in each repetition.

The main difference of the proposed method as compared to the ActIVO framework is that it does not rely on the explicit orthogonization of the uncertainty ellipsoid of the measurement with the uncertainty ellipsoid of the current task knowledge. In contrast, the LAIF control scheme solves the optimization problem on-line by following the moving camera towards the directions that minimize the uncertainty of the data fusion mechanism. This property enables the incorporation of possible occlusions in the scene. The LAIF framework is displayed in a block diagram form in Fig. 13. For more details, please refer to the paper included in Appendix A.4, while the Python (real experiments) and Matlab (simulation) implementation of the algorithm can be found in the following link, providing also a pseudocode: <https://github.com/CSRL-HMU/AIF-LbD>.

Figure 13 - Block diagram of the LAIF control scheme

Experimental evaluation of the LAIF scheme

A video of the experimental and simulation evaluations, can be found in this link: <https://youtu.be/ECnM2dK781w>. For the experimental validation, the UR5e robot is utilized, having an in-hand ZED 2 RGB-D camera sensor attached to its tip, while the Point Of Interest is considered to be the index finger of the human (note here that considering another point of interest, such as the hand wrist, is straight-forward, as per the requirements for the Integration of the overall CARPOS system). The framework was implemented using Python, while for the forward kinematic and the Jacobian of the robot, the Robotics Toolbox (<https://petercorke.com/toolboxes/robotics-toolbox/>) was utilized. For identifying the human fingers, the pre-trained “Mediapipe Hands” algorithm was utilized in real time, while for identifying any other objects (possibly occluding the field of view), YOLOv8 (<https://docs.ultralytics.com/models/yolov8/>) was employed. The latter detection algorithms were running on a separate (from the control loop) thread, in order to ensure that the control cycle, which was set to 2ms, is not affected.

For the experiments, the human was instructed to follow a predefined path annotated on a table, used as ground-truth for the evaluation, as shown in Fig. 14. No information regarding this path was provided to the proposed framework. For testing the performance of the proposed framework, we consider two cases. The first case involves the observation of the finger’s motion without considering any occlusions to the scene (Fig. 14a), while for the second case an obstacle (plastic mock-up fruit) was considered to intercept the view of the POI as seen by the camera, during a part of its motion (Fig. 14b). For detecting whether an occlusion occurs, we compare the depth of the fingertip’s estimate (provided by MediaPipe) to that of the object (identified by YOLOv8), if the finger’s position in the pixel space is within the bounding box of the object⁴. Lastly, three repetitions of the task were considered, since, during the third repetition, the uncertainty of the estimate was deemed already sufficiently minimized.

⁴ Notice that a simplified rationale was employed for this specific aspect, as the focus of the proposed framework is not towards the development of such detection algorithms

(a) The case of fully visible POI.

(b) View of the camera (case involving occlusions of POI)

Figure 14- Experimental evaluation of the LAIF control scheme

The experimental results demonstrated the minimization of the uncertainty achieved by the proposed method, as well as noise rejection, within a couple of repetitions.

APPENDIX A

A.1 - GRAsPAD: Generalized framework for optimal grasp key-points active detection. *(Accepted at the 34th IEEE International Conference on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (IEEE RO-MAN), Eindhoven, The Netherlands)*

GRAsPAD: Generalized framework for optimal grasp key-points active detection

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Abstract—In the challenging context of human-robot collaboration, the ability to capture critical human-grasp-related features in a short period is essential for the transfer of skills/experience and the effective imitation learning of human grasping strategies to robotic systems. The paper at hand introduces a novel system for pose optimization of an active (moving) sensor, reducing uncertainty in grasp perception and enabling a more accurate observation of the human grasp pose. The proposed framework, coined as "GRAsPAD" (Generalized fRAMework for optimal graSp key-Points Active Detection), leverages a keypoint detection model to identify grasp-related features in a tomato fruit. The camera pose is iteratively adjusted through the Covariance Matrix Adaptation with Margin - Evolution Strategy (CMAwM-ES) to minimize uncertainty in detected keypoints, enhancing the accuracy of grasp perception and ensuring a clearer, more stable grasp representation. To mitigate sensor noise and variability, a Kalman filter is applied to refine keypoint detections over time. The experimental results demonstrate the significant improvement achieved by the pose optimization of the observer, in terms of grasp perception quality, which is critical for robotic skill learning and effective transfer of human grasping strategies to robotic systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

In contemporary research, the advancement of robotic systems capable of swiftly, accurately, and safely assimilating human processes remains a formidable challenge. Addressing this issue necessitates the design of robust perception systems that can actively adapt their pose to find the optimal observation pose. Within the domain of active perception, the challenge of determining the "Next Best View" (NBV) was first introduced by C. Connolly [1] within the fields of computer vision and robotics. The term "active observer" refers to a sensor capable of adjusting its location and/or orientation in space, with NBV-based methods aiming to identify the optimal pose that maximizes the information about the observed object or scene. Since their first reference hitherto, NBV approaches have been adapted and utilized

in numerous areas—including 3D object reconstruction, autonomous robot navigation, and visual or quality inspection.

Several studies, address object or scene reconstruction, with a large portion of those studies utilizing machine learning techniques—such as 3D Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Curriculum and Reinforcement Learning (CRL), Point Cloud Networks, and Random Trees—to identify the next best view [2]–[5]. Additional applications include pose estimation [6], [7] and object recognition or classification [8], [9]. In robotics, NBV has been studied extensively in tasks like localization and navigation [10]–[14], grasping [15], [16], and calibration [17]–[19].

A crucial aspect of perception in robotics, particularly in agriculture and automated harvesting, is the detection and localization of objects in complex environments. In fruit-harvesting robots, vision systems must not only detect ripe and undamaged fruit but also accurately compute their 3D coordinates for robotic manipulation. Various techniques have been explored for fruit recognition, including image segmentation based on color models, feature detection, and machine learning approaches such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [20]. Additionally, visual servoing has been applied to dynamically adjust the pose of the robotic end-effector in response to occlusions and variations in fruit positioning, leveraging visual feedback for precise interaction [21]. Furthermore, researchers from Wageningen University [22], presented a framework for apple harvesting purposes, which uses gloves with OptiTrack markers to detect and track hand pose.

Although the aforementioned methods, have been used in many fields, their potential use for active optimal state estimation involving a human agent, aiming towards grasp identification, still needs to be investigated. Current approaches are limited around demanding models (RL models or Deep Neural Nets) or they count on external solutions (like gloves) which insert time limitations and consequently prevent them from being usable for human-to-robot skill transfer. In our previous work [23], an active perception framework was proposed for estimating the motion of the human hand, without however focusing on the human grasping.

In this work, in the context of Learning by Demonstration (LbD), we consider the problem of actively perceiving key features of the human grasping of a fruit. In particular, we consider the case in which the human is instructed to keep her/his hand still for the process, involving her/him in the

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active perception loop. As it is important for the human not to shoulder too much physical or cognitive load, the systems aims not only at providing accurate estimates of the features, but also at being fast for facilitating the human involvement and ensuring her/his comfort.

The current work's contributions are the following:

- A method for optimizing of sensor pose (which is considered to be attached to a mechanism) is proposed, allowing rapid adjustment of the sensor viewpoint to improve grasp comprehension.
- To minimize the human partner's physical and mental burden during the process, a clear balance between accuracy and efficiency is sought.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND CONCEPT SOLUTION

One of the key challenges in robotics is still grasping things in unstructured situations, especially for applications like agricultural harvesting. Consider a grasping scenario, such as picking a tomato fruit from a tree. The robot needs to initially identify the most efficient grasping position while accounting for occlusions, changing illumination, and the inherent diversity in the fruit's shape and orientation to do this task effectively.

In the context of Learning by Demonstration (LbD), we consider the case in which the human, who grasps the object, is instructed to keep her/his hand still in order for the system to acquire enough data for detecting the grasp pose. Furthermore, we consider the availability of a moving/actuated sensor, such as an RGB-D camera mounted on the robot's end-effector, to improve perception skills. This sensor can actively change its position and orientation within the 3D space, balancing exploration and exploitation tactics to improve its perspective, in contrast to static perception systems. A conceptual diagram of the considered problem is provided in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: The considered problem. From the initial to the optimal pose.

Let $\{S\}$ be the sensor frame and $\mathbf{c}_p \triangleq [\mathbf{p}_p^T \mathbf{q}_p^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{S}^3$ be the its pose, where $\mathbf{p}_p \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{q}_p \in \mathbb{S}^3$ are the position and orientation (in a unit quaternion form) of $\{P\}$, with respect to the inertial frame $\{0\}$ respectively, with $\mathbb{S}^n \triangleq \{\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} : \|\mathbf{a}\|=1\} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$, denoting the set of unit vectors in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} . Furthermore, let ${}^i\mathbf{x}(t) \triangleq {}^i\mathbf{p}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $i = 1, \dots, N$ be the states of the N observed key points, where ${}^i\mathbf{p}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the position of i -th key point respectively. Due to the fact that the human is instructed to not move her/his hand during the procedure, we consider the state propagation equation for the key-points' dynamics; namely ${}^i\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{0}, \forall i = 1, \dots, N$. As in a real-world case there are slight movements of grasping contact points and also of the detected key-points of fruit due to the lack of human hand's stability and jittering of sensors' detection, respectively, we consider the utilization of Linear Kalman filtering.

Given that the pose of the sensor, i.e. \mathbf{c}_p , is actuated, our aim is to design a framework that is able to efficiently explore and accurately estimate the best pose of the sensor, so that the key points of the grasp are optimally perceived, i.e. with minimal uncertainty.

III. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

We consider the availability of a trajectory planner and a trajectory tracking controller that are able to move the end-effector (with the camera) from its current pose, to a target pose $\mathbf{c}_p^* \in \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{S}^3$. One such an option, which is employed in our case, is the utilization of a 5th order polynomial as the trajectory planner and the Closed Loop Inverse Kinematics algorithm (CLIK) for accurately tracking the trajectory generated (for the orientation the logarithmic error is employed for the CLIK algorithm), as we consider a robot accepting joint velocity commands. The motion of the robot is considered to be confined within a subset of $\mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{S}^3$, e.g. the robot's work-space, parameterized by $\boldsymbol{\xi} \in \mathbb{R}^M$. For instance, if a sphere around a rough estimate of the center of the scene is considered to represent the allowable work-space of the end-effector, the polar coordinates can be utilized and therefore $\boldsymbol{\xi} \triangleq [\phi \ \theta] \in \mathcal{T}$, with $\mathcal{T} \subset \mathbb{R}^M$ the allowable subspace of the parameters defining the work-space of the robot. In other words, $\mathbf{c}_p^* \triangleq \mathbf{c}_p(\boldsymbol{\xi}^*)$, with $\boldsymbol{\xi}^* \in \mathcal{T}$ being the target parameters. Let us highlight that it is crucial that the trajectory generation mechanism should yield a trajectory which satisfies this constraint for all $t > 0$.

For tackling the considered problem, we combine linear Kalman filtering for estimating the state of the perceived key-points, with the Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy (CMA-ES) algorithm for efficient and fast exploration of the pose/task space of the sensor, as shown in Fig. 2. Preliminaries on both employed algorithms are provided below. Given the above rationale, the problem can be written, in a more mathematically rigorous form, as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\xi}^* = \arg \max_{\boldsymbol{\xi} \in \mathcal{T}} \mathcal{J}(\boldsymbol{\xi}), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{J}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ a reward function that reflects the information gain, which will be defined later.

Fig. 2: Conceptual diagram of the proposed solution

A. Preliminaries on linear Kalman filtering

The linear Kalman filter, introduced by Rudolf E. Kálmán [24], is a well-known method for state estimation of dynamical systems. The rationale behind Kalman filtering, is that the estimated state emerges from fusing measurements (which contains noise with known statistical properties) and prediction derived from the (theoretical) model of the observed phenomenon/object. In the core of the filter, a dynamic model of the observed system is utilized, which is considered to be known with a specific uncertainty. From a control theory perspective, Kalman filtering is an adaptable state observer that not only estimates the next state, $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, of a discrete-time (with $k \in \mathbb{N}$ representing the discrete time index) linear dynamical system, with n state variables, based on noisy observations, but also calculates the uncertainty for its estimations. Let the following be the considered discrete time model:

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{w}_k, \quad \mathbf{w}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{Q}_k), \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_k = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{v}_k, \quad \mathbf{v}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{\Sigma}_k), \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the model-predicted system state vector in next time step, i.e. $k+1$, $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the estimated system state vector at the current time step, $\mathbf{w}_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the process noise/disturbance with covariance $\mathbf{Q}_k \in S_{++}^n$, with S_{++}^n representing the set of $n \times n$ positive definite matrices. Then, $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the state transition matrix, $\mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the measured output of the system with $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ being the "so-called" observation matrix, and $\mathbf{v}_k \in \mathbb{R}^m$ the measurement noise, which is considered to be a random variable with covariance $\mathbf{\Sigma}_k \in S_{++}^m$.

The Kalman filter is structured around two key steps: (A) the prediction step and (B) the update step. The estimate is provided based on the following formulas:

A. Prediction Step:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} = \mathbf{F}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1|k-1}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{P}_{k-1|k-1}\mathbf{F}^T + \mathbf{Q}_k. \quad (5)$$

B. Update Step:

$$\mathbf{S}_k \triangleq \mathbf{H}\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1}\mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{\Sigma}_k \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_k \triangleq \mathbf{P}_{k|k-1}\mathbf{H}_k^T(\mathbf{S}_k)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} + \mathbf{K}_k(\mathbf{z}_k - \mathbf{H}_k\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1}), \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{k|k} = (\mathbf{I}_n - \mathbf{K}_k\mathbf{H}_k)\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1}, \quad (9)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1|k-1} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the estimated state of the previous time step, $\mathbf{P}_{k-1|k-1} \in S_{++}^n$ the estimated covariance of previous time step, $\mathbf{S}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is used for the covariance calculation of update stage, and $\mathbf{K}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ is the "so-called" Kalman gain. Lastly, $\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1}, \mathbf{P}_{k|k} \in S_{++}^n$ are the so-called "prior" and "posterior" covariance matrices, respectively, of the uncertainty of the estimate. Given these matrices, the information gain in each step k is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{J}_k \triangleq \log \frac{\det(\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1})}{\det(\mathbf{P}_{k|k})}. \quad (10)$$

The value defined in (10) is utilized in (1) for completing the definition of the optimization problem.

B. Preliminaries on CMA-ES

The Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy (CMA-ES) [25] is a stochastic optimization algorithm for black-box optimization problems. It maintains a multivariate normal distribution that evolves over generations. Given an optimization problem with $\mu \in \mathbb{N}$ tunable parameters, the objective is to seek and find one or more candidate solutions, $\boldsymbol{\xi}^* \in \mathbb{R}^\mu$, that minimize (or maximize) the so-called objective/cost/fitness (or reward) function, $\mathcal{J}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. The main idea of CMA-ES is to provide, in each iteration ("generation"), a number of candidate solution for the problem ("offspring"), based on a normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \mathbf{C}^{(g)})$ and a step $\sigma^{(g)} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$, with $\mathbf{C}^{(g)} \in S_{++}^\mu$ and $\sigma^{(g)} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ being adapted dynamically, where $g \in \{1, \dots, g_{max}\}$ is the generation/iteration index and $g_{max} \in \mathbb{N}$ the maximum number of generations.

The initialization of the CMA-ES algorithm requires the definition of the initial mean value ($\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}} = \boldsymbol{\xi}_0$), initial covariance matrix ($\mathbf{C}^{(1)} = \mathbf{C}_0$), initial step size ($\sigma^{(1)} = \sigma_0$), and the definition of $g_{max} \in \mathbb{N}$, as well as the number of offspring, $\lambda_{max} \in \mathbb{N}$. In the "sampling" stage, the algorithm generates λ_{max} offspring solutions (population size at each generation) by sampling a multivariate normal distribution:

$$\boldsymbol{\xi}_\lambda^{*(g+1)} \sim \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^{(g)} + \sigma^{(g)}\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{C}^{(g)}), \quad \lambda = 1, \dots, \lambda_{max} \quad (11)$$

where " \sim " denotes the same distribution on left and right side.

After the generation of the offspring, the algorithm updates the mean value $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^{(g)} \rightarrow \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^{(g+1)}$, the covariance $\mathbf{C}^{(g)} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}^{(g+1)}$ and the step $\sigma^{(g)} \rightarrow \sigma^{(g+1)}$, based on the mean values of the parents, the generated solutions and their previous values. More details about the CMA-ES algorithm can be found in [25].

C. Perception of the human grasp key-points

A vision-based keypoint detection system is integrated using an RGB-D camera. The perception system is composed based on two components: a) YOLOv11 Pose model [26] for the fruit detection and b) the Google's MediaPipe Hands model [27] for the human hand. The YOLOv11 model is trained to detect three structural keypoints on the tomato fruit—the center of the tomato ($\mathbf{p}_{t1} \in \mathbb{R}^3$), the "knee" on the peduncle ($\mathbf{p}_{t2} \in \mathbb{R}^3$), and the first junction of the peduncle

with the plant ($\mathbf{p}_{t3} \in \mathbb{R}^3$), as shown in Fig. 3. For the hand detection, the Google’s MediaPipe Hands model [27] is employed, which detects three keypoints of the hand, namely the wrist ($\mathbf{p}_{h1} \in \mathbb{R}^3$), the thumb tip ($\mathbf{p}_{h2} \in \mathbb{R}^3$), and the base of the middle finger ($\mathbf{p}_{h3} \in \mathbb{R}^3$), as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Key-points considered.

The YOLOv11 Pose model is able to detect bounding boxes and keypoints in parallel, with keypoints directly regressed as offsets from the bounding box anchor grid. This allows the model to estimate x and y coordinates, associated with a confidence, for each keypoint at multiple scales, using the bounding box as a reference frame. The confidence score indicates the model’s certainty about keypoint visibility, with values close to 1 signifying high confidence and those near 0 suggesting occlusion or uncertainty. The model was trained on an annotated dataset of 480 images, each containing multiple tomato instances, and evaluated on a validation set of 43 images. To ensure accurate object localization relative to the camera frame, the detected 2D keypoints are projected into 3D spatial coordinates using depth information and the camera’s intrinsic parameters.

In general, the RGB-D camera’s keypoint recognition yields depth measurements aligned with the object’s surface rather than its centroid. Therefore, for the detected keypoint $\mathbf{p}_{t1} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, which is assumed to be located at the center of the fruit, the provided position by the system is translated inward along the estimated surface normal by half of the object’s size, denoted with $d \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$, which is determined by the camera intrinsics and the bounding box width, in order to provide a more realistic representation:

$$d = \frac{(p_2 - p_1)\zeta}{2f_x}, \quad (12)$$

where $\zeta \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ is the average depth of a 3×3 array of pixels around the keypoint, $p_1, p_2 \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ are the horizontal pixel coordinates of the bounding box and f_x is the focal length in pixels. Then the surface normal, $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{S}^2$ is approximated by selecting four neighboring points around the keypoint and computing two tangent vectors, $\mathbf{t}_1, \mathbf{t}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^3$, as follows:

$$\mathbf{t}_1 = \mathbf{p}_b - \mathbf{p}_a, \quad \mathbf{t}_2 = \mathbf{p}_d - \mathbf{p}_c, \quad \mathbf{n} = \frac{\mathbf{t}_1 \times \mathbf{t}_2}{\|\mathbf{t}_1 \times \mathbf{t}_2\|} \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3, i \in \{a, b, c, d\}$, are the points corresponding to pixel locations to the left, right, top, and bottom of the detected keypoint, respectively. The computed normal vector \mathbf{n} is then used to adjust the keypoint inward along the estimated surface direction as follows:

$${}^c\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{t1} = \mathbf{p}_1 + d\mathbf{n}, \quad (14)$$

with ${}^c\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{t1} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denoting the position of the center of the fruit, with respect to the camera frame $\{C\}$. This adjustment ensures that the assigned reference frame originates at the center of the tomato rather than at its surface. Based on ${}^c\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{t1}$ and given the forward kinematics of the robot, one can easily yield the position of the key-point w.r.t. the inertial frame. Notice that, to establish a local reference frame for grasping, a coordinate system is constructed based on three detected tomato keypoints, given the three points $\mathbf{p}_{t1}, \mathbf{p}_{t2}, \mathbf{p}_{t3}$, which is however out of the scope of this work.

Hand detection is performed using a pre-trained MediaPipe Hand landmark model. In the first step, a Single-Shot Detector SSD-based palm detection model identifies bounding boxes and their corresponding confidence scores, which are then cropped and passed to the next stage. Then a second deep learning model takes the cropped hand image and directly yields the 21 anatomical hand keypoints. Since MediaPipe only provides relative depth values with respect to the wrist, absolute 3D world coordinates are reconstructed using the camera’s intrinsic parameters and depth projection equations. Leveraging the model’s predicted relative depth values in conjunction with the wrist’s depth provides more reliable results, particularly in cases of occlusion and self-occlusion, compared to directly using depth values at the x, y coordinates.

D. Synthesis of the proposed framework

Focusing on the architecture of the GRASPAD framework, two basic loops are identified: a) the optimization loop and the control loop. The outcome of the framework results from the smooth fusion of these components. Towards abstracting the idea of building the framework, it is important to mention that, two types of parameters are involved in our case. On the one hand, some are associated with the human and robot interaction and the task, such as the total time of the procedure and geometrical aspects of the work-space, such as the considered center of the scene and on the other hand the more technical ones are associated with software or hardware limitations. Some examples of the latter is the time step for the control loop.

For synthesizing the proposed solution, we consider the concatenation of the six key-points, i.e. the ones that are related to both the tomato and the human-hand, as the state of the system, and therefore the full state of the system is selected to be $\mathbf{x} \triangleq [\mathbf{x}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{x}_6^T]^T \triangleq [\mathbf{p}_{h1}^T, \mathbf{p}_{h2}^T, \mathbf{p}_{h3}^T, \mathbf{p}_{t1}^T, \mathbf{p}_{t2}^T, \mathbf{p}_{t3}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{18}$. Hence, in our case, the Kalman filter considers $n = m = 18$.

For defining the measurement uncertainty, we utilize the confidence for each key point of the tomato provided by the YOLOv11 model, as well as the confidence score of the palm

provided by Mediapipe (provided for the whole wrist). More specifically, let $\rho_{t1}, \rho_{t2}, \rho_{t3} \in [0, 1]$ be the confidence of the estimation of the tomato points for $\mathbf{p}_{t1}, \mathbf{p}_{t2}, \mathbf{p}_{t3}$ respectively, and let $\rho_h \in [0, 1]$ the confidence provided for the human hand. Then, the measurement covariance matrix is consider, in our method, to be:

$$\Sigma_k = (\mathbf{R}_{c,k} \otimes \mathbf{I}_6) \underbrace{(\mathbf{I}_6 - \text{diag}(\rho_{t1}, \rho_{t2}, \rho_{t3}, \rho_h, \rho_h, \rho_h))}_{\text{uncertainty of each key-point}},$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{c,k} \in SO(3)$ the rotation matrix describing the orientation of the camera with respect to the world frame at the k -the step, with " \otimes " denoting the Kronecker product. Notice that \mathbf{Q}_k and $\mathbf{P}_{0|0}$ are considered to be tunable parameters. Let us highlight, that when an estimate for a key-point is not provided by the perception algorithm, e.g. possibly due to not being within the field of view or not distinguishable, the corresponding uncertainty is set to a predefined relatively large value (approaching numerical infinity).

The proposed algorithm is depicted in Fig. 4. Notice that the reaching procedure is performed for each child (λ) of each generation (g) in a sequential manner. One important aspect is that the CMA-ES optimization solver is fed, in each optimization iteration, not only when the next target is reached, but also during and along the reaching procedure, in order to be able to exploit possible usable information about the reward. This sampling procedure is performed in a separate reward sampling loop, which lies, in term of frequency, between the fast control loop and the relatively slower high-level optimization loop. The selection of this sampling frequency is considered to be a tunable aspect.

Remark 1. *Although the method is presenting in the context of the grasp of a tomato fruit, it is straight-forward to extend its use to other objects and involving other key-points, by training the perception model accordingly, or even by utilizing a pre-trained model.*

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

For the experimental evaluation, the UR5e robotic manipulator is utilized with an eye-in-hand Realsense D435 RGB-D camera, as depicted in Fig.5. The proposed framework is implemented in Python and it is publicly available¹. For integrating the CMA-ES algorithm within our framework, the "cmaes" Python library is utilized. From this library the CMAwM (CMA-ES with margin) algorithm is employed, in order to ensure that the algorithm will be able to also handle cases in which the reward function exhibits a plateau, i.e. when its gradient of the reward is zero within a relatively large area. The maximum generations for the CMAwM-ES algorithm are set to $g_{max} = 5$, the population size in each generation is set to $\lambda_{max} = 6$, while the initial step is set to $\sigma_0 = 6$ and its initial mean value is set to correspond to the pose of the robot. Furthermore, the model error covariance is arbitrarily selected to be $\mathbf{Q}_k = 10\mathbf{I}_{18}$ and the initial covariance of the estimation is set to $\mathbf{P}_{0|0} = \mathbf{I}_{18}$. The

Fig. 4: Flow chart of the synthesized proposed solution.

trajectory generation and control loop's cycle is selected to be 20ms, while the total time duration for reaching the next candidate solution is set to 5s. The work-space of the robot is constraint on a hemisphere, $c_p(\xi)$, around the estimated center of the scene (which is more than 10cm far from the real center of the scene, for being realistic), with $\xi \triangleq [\phi \theta]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$, with $\theta, \phi \in [\pi/8, \pi/2 - 0.3]$.

For evaluating the framework, two experimental scenarios are considered: a) the active detection of a grasp using a mock up setup with a plastic fruit and a realistic plastic human hand, for extensive evaluation and comparison and b) the active detection of a real human grasping case, involving a real tomato for testing the performance of the method in different light conditions and possible occlusion.

Fig. 5: Experimental setup for the initial evaluation experiments.

¹<https://github.com/efnikos/GRAsPAD>

A. Extensive evaluation of GRASPAD framework in a mockup setup

For extensively evaluating the proposed method, we utilize a mock up setup with a plastic tomato and a human-like plastic hand, as shown in Fig. 5. This specific setup is selected in order to allow the "scanning" of the reward function within the considered workspace of the robot, in order to gain the ground-truth knowledge. To this aim, the workspace of the robot is uniformly sampled at 20×20 points within the ξ -space. For evaluating the performance of the proposed method, three different initial camera poses are considered, and 5 experiments are conducted from each initial pose, i.e. a total of 15 experiments were conducted for this evaluation.

The results of the scanned ground-truth reward, in a heatmap form, as well as the initial ξ_0 and optimal ξ^* found parameters through the proposed scheme are shown in Fig. 6. For presentation purposes, the data gathered from the scanning process are interpolated. Notice that in all 15 experiments the framework consistently identifies an optimal, or near-optimal, observation zone. Let us highlight that the initial view point from the third considered initial pose, i.e. the lowest parameter set within the blue shaded zone in Fig. 6, does not include any key-points from the tomato or the hand, i.e. the hand is initially outside the field of view. However, the proposed framework is able to find the solution, even in this challenging case in which the system is initiated from the center of a plateau. Lastly, let us highlight that the procedure of scanning the whole work-space required approximately 30 minutes, which is deemed to be restrictive given that the human is instructed to hold her/his hand still during the process. On the other hand, the proposed method only required 2.5 minutes (more than 10 times less).

Fig. 6: GRASPAD results over the ground-truth scanned via sampling.

B. Experiment with human and real fruit.

The second experiment involves a real human holding a tomato. Specifically, being aligned with typical real-world cases, two sub-cases are tested, namely a study testing two different light conditions, and a study involving occlusions within the field of view of the camera. The idea behind them was inspired from the fruit picking operations in greenhouses

where light conditions are rarely balanced and leaves or even branches can potentially occlude the view.

Figures 7a and 7b show the GRASPAD resulted view point of the grasp, while Fig. 7c and 7d depicts the resulted parameters ξ^* , as well as the initial ones. The surface in Fig. 7c and 7d are computed by interpolating the explored areas during the proposed optimization procedure. Let us highlight, also, that no key-points from the fruit or hand are visible from the initial view point, in order to challenge the exploration capabilities of the method. Notice how the proposed method remains unaffected by the lighting conditions and the observed key-point are detected with high confidence.

For emulating green-house conditions, a real branch with leaves, from a tomato plant, is placed between the workspace of the robot and the grasping location, to test the performance of the method in cases with occlusions of the view. Figure 8 shows the GRASPAD resulted view point of the grasp, in this case, alongside with the resulted parameter ξ^* . Notice how the reward changed with the existence of the branch, as compared to Fig. 7c and 7d, as the area exhibiting a high reward is significantly reduced in size. Lastly, notice that the proposed method was able to explore the workspace and find the view involving no occlusions, with the key-points being detecting with relatively high confidence.

(a) Balanced light conditions. (b) Imbalanced light exposure conditions.

(c) Results in the balanced light exposure case. (d) Results in the imbalanced light exposure case.

Fig. 7: Optimal resulted view points of the grasp, in two different lighting conditions, as well as the resulted optimal solution, in the parametric space.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a framework for actively perceiving grasp-related key-points is proposed, considering a robot with an eye-in-hand camera observing a human hand while grasping an object. The proposed framework, named "GRASPAD", leverages AI-based perception algorithms, such as the MediaPipe and YOLO, by combining them with state-of-the-art evolutionary optimization algorithms for finding

(a) Resulted view point, in the case involving occlusion. (b) Resulted parameters, in the case involving occlusion.

Fig. 8: Optimal resulted view points of the grasp, in the case in which occlusions are considered, as well as the resulted optimal solution in the parametric space.

the best view that minimizes the uncertainty. The method is extensively evaluated on a benchmarked mock up setup by conducting multiple experiments from different initial sensor poses, against the case of uniformly sampling the workspace for finding the optimal view-point. Furthermore, the performance of the proposed scheme is also tested on a realistic setup, involving a human and a real fruit, with varying lighting conditions and partial occlusions, emulating greenhouse environmental conditions. The outcomes disclosed that the proposed solution not only fulfills its objective to find the optimal observation pose, but also exhibits fast convergence to the solution, which is a crucial requirement due to the human being in-the-loop. In order to improve the generalizability and robustness of the method, future work will concentrate on expanding the framework's capabilities to dynamic environments with moving objects and human operators, incorporating active perception strategies, and validating the method across a larger range of tasks and robotic platforms.

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A.2 - ActIVO: An Active perception framework for skill transfer through Iterative Visual Observations *(Presented and included in the proceedings of the 32nd Mediterranean Conference on Control and Automation (IEEE MED), Chania, Greece)*

ActIVO: An Active perception framework for skill transfer through Iterative Visual Observations

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Abstract— Learning by demonstration (LbD) through visual observation is widely used in literature for tackling the problem of robot programming. However, identification and exact localization of the point of interest (e.g. human hand) during the demonstration, in most of the cases, comes with a non-negligible uncertainty, introduced by the detection algorithm and the sensor characteristics. In this work, we propose an active perception framework for gaining the maximum information during iterative demonstrations performed by a human, towards LbD. The method considers an in-hand camera and it is based on a covariance weighted pseudo-inverse estimator that accounts for the non-homogeneous uncertainty of the sensor. The proposed framework, coined as “ActIVO”, is experimentally validated in two scenarios, utilizing a UR5e robotic manipulator and an in-hand RealSense RGB-D camera.

I. INTRODUCTION

Explicit robot programming has been utilized in industrial settings for many decades. Despite the recent advancements in associated technological tools offered by robot manufacturers, explicit programming remains both technically demanding and time-intensive. These requirements become significantly more challenging when the robot has to operate in unstructured environments, such as in agricultural applications, where its motion must be adaptable to varying targets and environmental geometries, while often involving motion patterns that are difficult to define analytically. A pertinent example is the task of fruit picking, where the robot must execute precise motions to detach the fruit from the plant’s branch. In this context, the fruit’s position, orientation, and size can vary on each occasion, while the manipulation for detachment often involves intricate motions. The latter can be difficult to program explicitly and may differ for each fruit, underscoring the need for more flexible and adaptive robotic programming approaches.

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Learning by Demonstration (LbD), was recently proposed for tackling the problem of robot programming. According to LbD, the motion is taught to the robot based on a set of motion demonstrations [1], [2]. In most of the cases, these motion demonstrations are performed by a human and they are captured either utilizing proprioceptive data (e.g. robot encoders), when the robot is physically guided by the human-teacher [3], [4], or through external sensors, e.g. by visually observing the motion using a camera [5], [6]. Although LbD through visual observations is more intuitive and less cognitively and physically demanding for the human-teacher, it incorporates a relatively larger uncertainty, due to sensor noise, estimation errors and/or possible occlusions [7]. It is worth noting that, in the current literature, such LbD methods utilise only passive observations of the task, i.e. a static camera is considered.

Active perception (or “Active vision”, when a camera sensor is considered) is a notion introduced to tackle the problem of maximizing the information gained regarding an object of interest [8]–[10]. Active perception is inspired by biological systems, like humans, which intentionally act in order to acquire information, rather than relying on passive observations. Active perception methods have been utilized across various domains, including industrial [11], [12] and agricultural sectors [13], [14], as well as in robotic manipulation through reinforcement learning [10]. Some of the active perception controllers are based on the perceived geometry of the environment [14]–[16], while others employ machine learning for finding the optimal policies [13], [17], or even movement primitives models [11]. While active perception finds application across a wide range of tasks, to the best of the authors’ knowledge, it has not previously been explored for addressing the problem of LbD through active observation of human behavior.

In this context, our present work considers the case in which the motion of a point on the human hand (e.g. fingertip) is taught to the robot through iterative visual observations of demonstrations performed by a human-teacher. Such a task could involve the manipulation of a fruit for picking it, i.e. harvesting without a cutting tool, in which the farmer could transfer their life-long experience by performing a number of demonstrations with the robot observing their actions. The action is observed using an in-hand camera, i.e. a camera attached to the end-effector of the robot. Given the uncertainty involved in the 3D-position estimate provided by the visual sensor, we aim at iteratively minimizing the

uncertainty of the gathered information related to the motion executed by the tips of the human fingers. Gathering the maximum information, and consequently minimizing the uncertainty related to the trajectory followed by the human-hand, plays a crucial role on the learning performance and could significantly reduce the number of iterations required for skill transfer. To achieve this, we propose an active perception framework, based on a covariance weighted pseudo-inverse estimator.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND CONCEPT SOLUTION

Let us consider a robotic system with an in-hand RGB-D camera, i.e. a camera attached to its end-effector. Let $\{C\}$ be the frame of the camera and $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be the joint variables of the robot, with $n \geq 6$ being the number of its joints. Further, let the robotic system be kinematically controlled, i.e. accepting joint velocity commands $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_c(t)$. Our aim is through multiple iterative demonstrations, to move the camera such that the total uncertainty of the gathered information related to the position of the human fingertip is minimized. Furthermore, we consider that the uncertainty characterizing the camera (visual sensor) measurements is not homogeneous with respect to the frame of the camera.

The mapping between the generalized velocity of $\{C\}$ and the joint velocities are given by:

$$\mathbf{v}_c = \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q})\dot{\mathbf{q}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times n}$ is the Jacobian matrix of the robot and $\mathbf{v}_c \triangleq [\dot{\mathbf{p}}_c^T \ \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_c^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the generalized velocity with $\mathbf{p}_c, \boldsymbol{\omega}_c \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being the position of the camera and its angular velocity respectively.

Let $\mathbf{p}_{cf} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the actual position of the fingertip with respect to the camera frame $\{C\}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ its estimate provided by the camera utilizing a specific human hand detection algorithm; as depicted in Fig.1. The estimation error is then given by $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf} - \mathbf{p}_{cf}$. Let $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c \triangleq \text{var}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \in S_{++}^3$ be the variance-covariance matrix of the probability distribution¹ of $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, with respect to the camera frame $\{C\}$. Note that $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c$, not only captures the accuracy and characteristics of the sensor, but also incorporates errors introduced by the detection algorithm. We assume that an estimate of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c$ is either directly available or can be statistically extracted from a sufficiently large dataset of measurements.

In the context of human hand tracking with an RGB-D sensor, while the human hand is reliably tracked in the $x-y$ plane of the camera (i.e. the pixel space of the camera's RGB output), the estimation of depth often involves considerable uncertainty, mainly due to the sensitivity and low robustness of the depth estimation mechanism. In particular, the distance estimation can be affected by external infrared exposure, such as sunlight (in case the RGB-D camera uses an infrared pattern), the reflective properties of the material, or even the color of the object. Moreover, most RGB-D cameras employ a spatial low-pass smoothing filter for depth information, introducing further error into depth measurement.

¹A normal distribution is considered.

Fig. 1: Uncertainty of the camera estimation.

Taking into account all these factors, we consider the uncertainty of the measurement along the z -axis of the RGB-D camera to be higher than that along the other axes. Consequently, we assume the estimated covariance matrix for the RGB-D camera with respect to the camera frame $\{C\}$, to be as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_d \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is the variance of the measurement along the x and y axes, while $\sigma_d > \sigma \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is the variance along the z axis of the camera. Note that $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c$ is assumed to be constant, as it reflects the characteristics of the camera with respect to its frame. Let $\mathbf{p}_c(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_c(t) \in SO(3)$ be the position and orientation (expressed in a rotation matrix form) of the camera, respectively, w.r.t. the inertial frame $\{0\}$. Further, let $\mathbf{p}_f(t) = \mathbf{p}_c(t) + \mathbf{R}_c(t)\mathbf{p}_{cf}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the actual position of the fingertip in time and $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t) = \mathbf{p}_c(t) + \mathbf{R}_c(t)\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be its estimate captured by the camera in a single observation with respect to the inertial frame $\{0\}$, with $t \in [0, T]$ and $T \in \mathbb{R}^+$ being the duration of the demonstration. The covariance matrix of the estimation error of the camera with respect to the inertial frame $\{0\}$ is then given by:

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}(t) = \mathbf{R}_c(t)\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c\mathbf{R}_c^T(t). \quad (3)$$

It is therefore easily inferred, given the above rationale and assumptions, that the motion can not be perfectly or even accurately captured and/or reconstructed by a single observation, and that multiple observations from different viewpoints would contribute to the improvement of the reliability of the measurements.

Our goal is to estimate the position of a moving human fingertip, i.e. $\mathbf{p}_f(t)$, following an iterative procedure, in which the total uncertainty of the estimate $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t)$ is minimized in each iteration. To achieve this, we propose a novel framework including a) a covariance weighted least square estimator [18] based on multiple demonstrations of the same task performed by the human and captured by the camera, and b) a novel active perception control policy that moves the camera on-line, such that the uncertainty of the total captured data is minimized. The proposed control scheme aims at yielding a gradually more homogeneous and lower total uncertainty (given the current and the previous captured data) along the axes of \mathbb{R}^3 . In other words, our goal is to make the eigenvalues of the total covariance matrix gradually equal, for all $t \in [0, T]$, given that the human performs a number of motion demonstrations of the same task, in order to increase the quality of motion reconstruction.

III. MOTION RECONSTRUCTION FROM MULTIPLE OBSERVATIONS

Given that m demonstrations of the same task are performed by the human, let $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,i}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the estimated position of the fingertip captured by the camera in the i -th iteration, where $t \in [0, T_i]$ with $T_i \in \mathbb{R}^+$ being the duration of the i -th demonstration, $i = 1, \dots, m$. Let the field of view of the camera be different in each iteration, a condition that will be ensured by the active perception controller detailed in the next Section. Also, let $\mathbf{p}_{c,i}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_{c,i}(t) \in SO(3)$ be the position and the rotation matrix, respectively, of the camera during the i -th iteration (observation). In order to exploit the multiple demonstrations of the task, we must synchronize the trajectories. To achieve this, one can consider the first iteration as the reference one and synchronize the others by searching for the closest position of this trajectory to the task-space estimate of each iteration, given by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,i}(t) = \mathbf{p}_{c,i}(t) + \mathbf{R}_{c,i}(t)\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,i}(t), \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,i}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,i}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ are the estimated position of the fingertip with respect to the camera's frame $\{C\}$ and the inertial frame $\{0\}$, respectively. Therefore, and for simplicity of the presentation, for the rest of the paper, consider $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,i}(t)$, $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,i}(t)$, $\mathbf{p}_{c,i}(t)$, $\mathbf{R}_{c,i}(t)$ be the temporally scaled variables. Hence, for the rest of the paper, $T_i = T, \forall i = 1, \dots, m$.

In order to exploit the multiple observations and the knowledge (or estimate) of the covariance matrix of the camera measurement, we propose the utilization of a covariance weighted least square estimator. Based on this estimator, the estimate of the position of the fingertip, after the completion of the m -th iteration is obtained from:

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t) = \mathbf{A}^{\mathcal{L}}(t) \left(\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{P}_c(t) + \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}(t) \right), \quad (5)$$

where

$$\mathbf{B}(t) \triangleq \text{diag} \left(\mathbf{R}_{c,i}^{\top}(t) \right) \in \mathbb{R}^{3m \times 3m}, i = 1, \dots, m, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_c(t) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_{c,1}(t) \\ \mathbf{p}_{c,2}(t) \\ \dots \\ \mathbf{p}_{c,m}(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}(t) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,1}(t) \\ \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,2}(t) \\ \dots \\ \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,m}(t) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{3m} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\mathbf{A}^{\mathcal{L}}(t) \triangleq (\mathbf{A}^{\top}\mathbf{W}\mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{A}^{\top}\mathbf{W}, \quad (8)$$

the covariance weighted left pseudo-inverse of \mathbf{A} with

$$\mathbf{W} \triangleq \mathbf{I}_m \otimes \Sigma_c^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{3m \times 3m}, \quad (9)$$

$\mathbf{I}_m \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ the identity matrix, " \otimes " denoting the Kronecker product (i.e. \mathbf{W} is a block diagonal matrix with Σ_c^{-1} in each block-element of its main diagonal) and

$$\mathbf{A}(t) \triangleq [\mathbf{R}_{c,1}(t) \ \mathbf{R}_{c,2}(t) \ \dots \ \mathbf{R}_{c,m}(t)]^{\top} \in \mathbb{R}^{3m \times 3}. \quad (10)$$

Lemma 1. *The covariance of $\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{P}_c(t) + \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}$ is equal to \mathbf{W}^{-1} .*

Proof. For $\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{P}_c(t) + \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}$ it holds:

$$\text{var}(\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{P}_c(t) + \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}) = \text{var}(\hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}), \quad (11)$$

as $\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{P}_c(t)$ is considered free of any uncertainty. After taking into account $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf} = \mathbf{P}_{cf} + [\varepsilon_1^{\top} \ \varepsilon_2^{\top} \ \dots \ \varepsilon_m^{\top}]^{\top}$, where $\varepsilon_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the estimation error in the i -th iteration, (11) becomes:

$$\text{var}(\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{P}_c(t) + \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}) = \text{var} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \dots \\ \varepsilon_m \end{bmatrix} \right) = \mathbf{I}_m \otimes \Sigma_c = \mathbf{W}^{-1}. \quad (12)$$

□

Remark 1. *Equation (5) gives the weighted least square solution of the following system:*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R}_{c,1}^{\top}(t)\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t) &= \mathbf{R}_{c,1}^{\top}(t)\mathbf{p}_{c,1}(t) + \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,1}(t), \\ \mathbf{R}_{c,2}^{\top}(t)\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t) &= \mathbf{R}_{c,2}^{\top}(t)\mathbf{p}_{c,2}(t) + \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,2}(t), \\ &\dots \\ \mathbf{R}_{c,m}^{\top}(t)\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t) &= \mathbf{R}_{c,m}^{\top}(t)\mathbf{p}_{c,m}(t) + \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,m}(t), \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

with respect to $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t)$. Notice that (13) yields after multiplying with $\mathbf{R}_{c,i}^{\top}(t)$ both sides of (4) for every iteration i . In particular, as the solution is weighted using the inverse of the covariance matrix of the camera, (5) gives the solution of the system (13), by assigning greater significance to the axis in which the covariance of the measurement is lower.

Proposition 1. *The total covariance matrix of the estimate computed from (5), after the data accumulation of m iterations, is given by:*

$$\bar{\Sigma}_m(t) = (\mathbf{A}^{\top}\mathbf{W}\mathbf{A})^{-1} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^m \Sigma_i^{-1} \right)^{-1}, \quad (14)$$

where $\Sigma_i(t) \triangleq \mathbf{R}_{c,i}(t)\Sigma_c\mathbf{R}_{c,i}^{\top}(t)$ is the individual covariance matrix of the i -th iteration with respect to the inertial frame $\{0\}$.

Proof. Taking into account (5), the covariance of the estimate after the m -th demonstration is the following:

$$\bar{\Sigma}_m(t) \triangleq \text{var}(\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t)) = \mathbf{A}^{\mathcal{L}} \text{var} \left(\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{P}_c(t) + \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf} \right) (\mathbf{A}^{\mathcal{L}})^{\top}. \quad (15)$$

After substituting (8) and applying Lemma 1 to (15), we get (14). □

To provide insight into how the total covariance of measurements, $\bar{\Sigma}_m$, changes with each new iteration-demonstration, a numerical example is presented in Fig. 2 for two scenarios. In the first case (left column of Fig. 2), two observations are considered, and the ellipsoids of the individual covariance of the two demonstrations are orthogonal, i.e. $\Sigma_1 \perp \Sigma_2$. Notice that in this ideal case, the resulted total covariance $\bar{\Sigma}_2$ (after the 2nd iteration), is already homogeneous (spherical). In the second case (right column of Fig. 2), three observations are considered, with the ellipsoids of the individual observations not being orthogonal

to each other. Notice that, in this more realistic case, the resulted total covariance $\bar{\Sigma}_3$ (after the 3rd iteration), tends also to be homogeneous.

Fig. 2: An example of two orthogonal observations and that of multiple observations.

IV. PROPOSED CONTROL SCHEME

Let us assume that the user performs the $(m + 1)$ -th demonstration. In this case, the total covariance matrix of the data, accumulated through the previous m iterations, is given by (14). Let, $\mathbf{n}_d \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the eigenvector of $\bar{\Sigma}_m(t)$ with largest corresponding eigenvalue, for a given $t \in [0, T]$, i.e. its major axis. Our control objectives are two:

- 1) To align the axis of the camera having the lowest uncertainty (minor axis, i.e. the sensor's most reliable axis), denoted by $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, with \mathbf{n}_d . In essence, we seek to minimize uncertainty along the axis where the current total uncertainty is maximum, or, put more simply, we aim to observe the scene from the viewpoint where uncertainty is highest, given all previous observations.
- 2) To keep the fingertip at the center of the field-of-view of the camera as much as possible and the distance of the camera from the fingertip equal to d , where $d \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is the nominal constant observation distance, which is dependent on the minimum distance that the camera can provide depth estimation.

To this end, and given the mapping given in (1), we propose the following control law, in the form of commanded joint velocities, which is composed by the superimposition of two intermediate control signals, \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_2 , one for each control objective respectively:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_c \triangleq \mathbf{J}^\dagger(\mathbf{q}) (\mathbf{v}_1 + \mathbf{v}_2), \quad (16)$$

where

$$\mathbf{v}_1 \triangleq k_a \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{R}_c \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}) \\ \mathbf{I}_3 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{n}_d) \in \mathbb{R}^6 \quad (17)$$

Fig. 3: Depiction of control signal $\mathbf{v}_1 + \mathbf{v}_2$.

is the intermediate control signal for aligning (reaching) the minor axis of the covariance of the camera (Σ_{m+1}) to the major axis of the total covariance of the currently gathered data ($\bar{\Sigma}_m$), and

$$\mathbf{v}_2 \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_c & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{R}_c \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_p (\|\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}\| - d) \frac{\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}}{\|\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}\|} \\ k_o \mathbf{u}([0 \ 0 \ 1]^\top, \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^6 \quad (18)$$

is the intermediate control signal for centering and maintaining the distance d from $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}$. In (16)-(18), $k_a, k_p, k_o \in \mathbb{R}^+$ are positive tunable gains, while

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \triangleq \text{acos} \left(\frac{\mathbf{a}^\top \mathbf{b}}{\|\mathbf{a}\| \|\mathbf{b}\|} \right) \frac{\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{a})\mathbf{b}}{\|\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{a})\mathbf{b}\|} \in \mathbb{R}^3 \quad (19)$$

indicates the minimum rotation (in angle-axis form) between any two vectors $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{S}(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ the skew-symmetric matrix, and $\mathbf{J}^\dagger \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 6}$ a pseudoinverse (the inverse, if $n = 6$) of $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q})$.

To get a better understanding of the rationale behind the design of the control signal, Fig.3 illustrates the action of the two intermediate control signals, \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_2 . Note that \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_2 act as virtual velocities on the robot's end-effector (in-hand camera). In particular, \mathbf{v}_1 acts as a virtual velocity that simply pivots the camera around the point of interest, utilizing reaching control, in order to align \mathbf{n} to \mathbf{n}_d . The translation part of \mathbf{v}_2 is a control signal that guides the camera's position to a distance of d from the point of interest. Note that the translation parts of \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_2 are orthogonal, and therefore their action is not affected by each other. The rotational part of \mathbf{v}_2 attracts the z -axis of the camera towards the vector pointing to the point of interest, for attracting the latter towards the center of the field of view. Notice that the equilibrium of the rotational part of \mathbf{v}_1 is also an equilibrium for the rotational part of \mathbf{v}_2 .

Remark 2. Note that \mathbf{v}_1 induces a simple first order attractor, which does not involve the rate of change of the major axis $\mathbf{n}_d(t)$. Therefore, although this part of the control scheme is expected to asymptotically converge for a constant \mathbf{n}_d , its performance is affected when $\dot{\mathbf{n}}_d(t) \neq \mathbf{0}$.

Hence, although $\mathbf{n}(t)$ is attracted to $\mathbf{n}_d(t)$, in general, a non negligible error is expected to exist between $\mathbf{n}(t)$ and $\mathbf{n}_d(t)$.

Remark 3. Note that the considered covariance matrix of the camera, given in (2), even when expressed w.r.t. the inertial frame, has two same minimum eigenvalues equal to σ . Consequently, determining \mathbf{n} is not straightforward. In this case, one has to select a vector that belongs to the plane defined by the two minor eigenvectors of this matrix.

V. THE PROPOSED COMPLETE LBD FRAMEWORK

Lastly, we integrate the motion reconstruction mechanism and the control scheme presented above in a unified Learning by Demonstration framework, available at the following github repository: <https://github.com/CSRL-HMU/ActiVO>, which is presented in Algorithm 1.

The complete framework involves multiple iterations of demonstrations, whose number can be either predefined, or determined by reaching a target uncertainty level, as shown in Algorithm 1. As a measure of the current uncertainty level, the volume and/or sphericity of the ellipsoid of the total covariance, i.e. $\bar{\Sigma}_m$, could be utilized. Furthermore, in the first iteration (see the “if $i = 1$...” conditions in Algorithm 1), only \mathbf{v}_2 is active for centering and maintaining the distance from the point of interest, as no previous demonstrations are available. Finally, we designate the reference time variable t_r from the first demonstration, which serves as the reference trajectory for synchronizing all time series.

After the calculation of the complete trajectory estimate $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t_r)$ (at the end of the algorithm), an one-shot encoding mechanism can be utilized to encode the motion based on this estimate. Such a mechanism could be the Dynamic Movement Primitives model [19], [20].

VI. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The proposed framework was evaluated experimentally utilizing a UR5e robotic manipulator with an Intel RealSense D415 RGB-D camera attached to its end-effector. For the kinematics of the robot, the Python version of the *Robotics toolbox* [21] was utilized. The frame rate of the camera was set to 30 fps and the control cycle of the robot was set to 2 ms. For the human hand detection and localization, the “Mediapipe Hands” [22] algorithm was employed, pre-trained with a sample of 16,000 real and 100,000 artificially generated human hand images. The hand detection algorithm and the control loop were running on different threads to ensure that the timing of the control loop remained unaffected.

For evaluating the framework, two experiments were conducted, the first considering a simple path of pre-determined geometry on a flat surface, and the second considering a fruit picking operation. In each iteration, an audio cue, signifying the initiation of the demonstration, was provided to the human, triggered as soon as the human hand was perceived by the camera. The y -axis of the camera was selected to represent \mathbf{n} (based on Remark 3) and the camera’s initial pose for each iteration was selected to be roughly orthogonal to the previous view-point of the camera. To synchronize signals across iterations, we identified the closest point on

Algorithm 1 Proposed LbD framework

```

1: Inputs:  $\Sigma_c, d, dt$  ▷ Camera and robot properties
2: Select values for:  $k_a, k_p, k_o$ 
3: for each demonstration  $i$  do
4:    $t := 0$  ▷ Initialization
5:   while  $t_r < T_r$  do
6:     Get  $\mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{R}_c, \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q})$ 
7:     Get  $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}$  from camera
8:      $t := t + dt$ 
9:     if  $i = 1$  then ▷ 1st iteration
10:       $t_r := t$ 
11:       $\mathbf{v}_1 := \mathbf{0}_6$  ▷ No prev. demos
12:      Calculate  $\mathbf{v}_2$  from (18)
13:       $\bar{\Sigma}_m(t_r) := \Sigma_i$  ▷ Initialization
14:    else
15:      Find the corresponding  $t_r$  of the 1st demo.
16:       $\mathbf{n}_d :=$  major eigenvector of  $\bar{\Sigma}_m(t_r)$ 
17:      Calculate current  $\Sigma_i$  from (3)
18:       $\bar{\Sigma}_m(t_r) := \left( \bar{\Sigma}_m^{-1}(t_r) + \Sigma_i^{-1} \right)^{-1}$  ▷ Eq. (14)
19:      Calculate  $\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2$  from (17), (18)
20:    end if
21:    Calculate  $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_c$  from (16)
22:    Command  $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_c$  to the robot
23:    Store  $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}$  as a sequence of  $t_r$ 
24:    Store  $\mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{R}_c$  as a sequence of  $t_r$ 
25:    Store  $\bar{\Sigma}_m$  as a sequence of  $t_r$ 
26:    if  $i = 1$  AND user commands break then
27:       $T_r := t_r$ 
28:      Break
29:    end if
30:  end while
31:  if Target uncertainty reached then
32:    Break
33:  end if
34: end for
35: Define  $\mathbf{W}$  from (9)
36: Calculate  $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{P}_c, \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}$  from (10), (6), (7)
37: Calculate  $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f$  sequence from (5) ▷ Estimator
38: Train an encoding mechanism (e.g. a DMP), based on
    the  $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f$  sequence of  $t_r$ 

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the trajectory of the first iteration (considered the reference trajectory) to the current position of the robot, within a window of 500 samples ahead in time. For facilitating this procedure a first order low-pass IIR filter² with a cutoff frequency of 5 rad/s was applied to the reference trajectory.

Since the lower end of the camera’s depth range is ~ 25 cm, the nominal observation distance was set at $d = 0.3$ m, while the other parameters of the framework were specified as $k_p = k_a = 1, k_o = 2, \sigma = 0.001$ and $\sigma_d = 0.05$. At the end of the procedure, the reconstructed trajectory, i.e. $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t)$, was encoded using a Dynamic Movement Primitives

²The low-pass filter was utilized only for the synchronization and not for the final motion estimation.

Fig. 4: Experimental setup for (a) hand movement along a pre-defined elliptical path, and (b) fruit picking emulation.

(DMP) model, involving 20 Gaussian kernels; the evolution of the DMP is denoted by $\mathbf{p}_{dmp}(t)$.

A video containing footage from these experiments can be found in https://youtu.be/0_M8fTugfyY.

A. Hand movement along a simple pre-determined path

The first experiment considered a simple task, where the human was instructed to move his hand along an annotated segment of an ellipse, drawn on a flat surface, as depicted in Fig. 4a. For this experiment, the position of the tip of the subject's index finger was designated as the point of interest. The experiment involved two iterations/observations of the task, as the sphericity of Σ_2 was deemed already sufficient for the signal reconstruction after the second iteration.

The path perceived by the camera in each iteration ($\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,1}(t)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,2}(t)$), as well as the reconstructed one, based on ActIVO, motion ($\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t)$) and the time evolution of the DMP model ($\mathbf{p}_{dmp}(t)$) are depicted in Fig. 5. Notice the smoothness of the estimated trajectory, $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t)$, and the encoded trajectory, $\mathbf{p}_{dmp}(t)$, as compared to the individually perceived trajectories in each iteration ($\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,1}(t)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,2}(t)$).

To provide insight into how the total covariance of measurements, $\bar{\Sigma}_m$, changes with each new iteration-demonstration, the covariance ellipsoids of each iteration (Σ_1, Σ_2), as well as the total one after the two iterations ($\bar{\Sigma}_2$), are depicted in Fig. 6 for a random time instance $t_r = t_1$ (t_r represents the synchronized common for all iterations). Notice how the considered total uncertainty (after iteration 2), represented by the ellipsoid of $\bar{\Sigma}_2$, is approximately spherical, having significantly less volume (i.e. less uncertainty) than the ones reflected by the perceived data during the first and second iterations.

B. Fruit picking emulation

The second experiment considered the emulation of a fruit picking operation, utilizing a mock-up setup with a plastic fruit (see Fig. 4b). For this experiment, the position of the tip of the thumb of the human was the designated point of interest, as the emulated scenario involved detaching the fruit by applying pressure to the branch with the thumb. As with the previous experiment, this case involved two iterations/observations of the task.

Fig. 5: Motion reconstruction for the experiment involving the pre-determined ellipsoidal path.

Fig. 6: Covariance ellipsoids for $t_r = t_1$.

The path of the thumb perceived by the camera in each iteration $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,1}(t)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,2}(t)$, as well as the proposed reconstructed motion $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t)$ and the time evolution of the DMP model $\mathbf{p}_{dmp}(t)$, are depicted in Fig. 7, while Fig. 8 shows the corresponding coordinates in time. A notable spike in the perceived position is evident in the first iteration (blue line) around $t_r \approx 1.2$ s, primarily attributed to an error in the camera's depth estimation. It is important to highlight that relying solely on a single observation from one viewpoint, such as that of the first iteration, would result in significantly erroneous thumb position estimates, potentially exhibiting high rates or even discontinuities. However, the proposed method effectively eliminates this spike by taking into account data from the second iteration and considering the non-homogeneous uncertainty of the sensor in the estimation process, in particular the fact that the error predominantly occurs along the z -axis of the camera during the first iteration. Indeed, the dotted line in Fig. 7 depicts the estimated trajectory without axis weighting based on covariance, i.e. by simply computing the mean of the perceived trajectories, $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t_r) = 0.5(\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,1}(t_r) + \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,2}(t_r))$. It is worth noting how this approach is influenced by the spike at $t_r \approx 1.2$ s.

Fig. 7: Motion reconstruction for the fruit picking emulation experiment.

Fig. 8: Time evolution of observations, estimate (based on ActIVO) and DMP model.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In the context of Learning by Demonstration through visual observations, we have proposed ActIVO, an active perception framework for minimizing the uncertainty during iterative demonstrations performed by a human. The framework considers an eye-in-hand visual sensor and it is based on a covariance weighted pseudo-inverse estimator, based on an estimate of the non-homogeneous uncertainty of the visual sensor. The proposed framework is experimentally evaluated in two scenarios. The experiments clearly demonstrate the improved motion reconstruction performance attained by utilizing ActIVO, as compared to a single-shot reconstruction or a non-weighted pseudo-inverse estimation. In the future, the utilization of Extended and/or Unscented Kalman Filters (EKF and UKF respectively) will be investigated in order to exploit the Dynamical Movement Primitive model trained

based on the previous demonstrations.

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A.3 - Optimized UKF-based perception of a repetitive dynamic event *(Presented and included in the proceeding of the 23rd European Control Conference (ECC) in Thessaloniki, Greece)*

Optimized UKF-based perception of a repetitive dynamic event

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Abstract— Living beings are rarely passive observers. Instead, they are characterized by a "Perception-Action Coupling", i.e. they perceive in order to move and they move in order to perceive, which constitutes an essential loop for learning. Drawing inspiration from nature, this work proposes a novel method for minimizing the uncertainty of the information gathered when observing a Repetitive Dynamic Event (RDE), considering a sensor that can change its position and orientation. The method considers an Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) for fusing the sensor's measurements with the evolution of the current dynamical model of the observed RDE. The proposed method aims at finding the optimum UKF parameters and pose of the sensor, for maximizing the quality of the estimation. Simulation and experimental evaluations show the improvement achieved by the proposed method, as compared to using a non-optimized UKF, in terms of the quality of acquired information of a dynamic event. The experiments are conducted using a UR10e robotic manipulator with an eye-in-hand ZED 2 RGB-D camera.

I. INTRODUCTION

A Repetitive Dynamic Event (RDE) is considered to be an event, characterized by specific dynamics, that re-occurs in a repetitive manner. RDEs can be either natural, e.g. frequent gas or liquid leakage, swinging objects, motion of leaves during a day etc, or artificial, e.g. the execution of experiments for modelling a system or the execution of demonstrations by a human towards Learning from Demonstration (LbD) of a task. To model the RDEs (or to learn, in case of LbD), one has to accurately observe and perceive the system's state. The uncertainty involved in the state perception/estimation, e.g. due to measurements error, plays a significant role on the quality of modelling.

In the context of active perception, the problem of finding the so-called "Next Best View" (NBV) was firstly introduced in the field of computer vision and robotics by C.Connolly [1]. NBV-based solutions consider an active observer, i.e. a sensor having the ability to change its position and/or orientation in space, and aim towards finding the optimum pose of the sensor for maximizing the information gathered about the perceived object/scene. Since their first appearance, NBV methods have been expanded and applied across many fields and applications, such as 3D object reconstruction,

robot autonomous navigation, visual and quality inspection. In the literature, most works tackle the problem of object/scene reconstruction, with the majority of them employing machine learning, such as 3D Convolution Neural Networks, Curriculum and Reinforcement Learning, Point Cloud Networks and Random Trees, for finding the next best view [2]–[5]. Other applications involve pose estimation [6], [7], object recognition/classification [8], [9], while in the field of robotics, NBV has been particularly studied also in applications such as localization [10], [11], robot grasping [12], [13], trajectory planning and robot navigation [14]–[16], or even calibration [17]–[19]. Although, the notion of NBV has been considered in all the aforementioned fields, to the best of the authors' knowledge, it has not been previously employed to tackle the problem of actively estimating the state of an RDE, as they mainly consider static objects or scenes.

Kalman filtering, initially introduced by Rudolf E. Kálmán [20], is a state estimation technique, which is based on a dynamic model, possessing a certain uncertainty. According to Kalman filtering the estimate is calculated by fusing the measurement, which is assumed to incorporate a noise with known statistical characteristics, and the prediction based on the model of the observed phenomenon. As the original Kalman filter considers a linear model, more recent variants are proposed for handling non-linearities, with the most popular being the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) and the Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) [21]. The advantage of UKF over EKF is that it employs statistical methods for inferring the Jacobian matrix of the system and therefore no analytic expression if it is required.

In this work, considering an active sensor, we propose a method that seeks for the optimal parameters and Next Best View, in order to minimize the uncertainty involved in the perception and estimation of the state of an RDE during its next occurrence (if natural) or execution (if artificial). The proposed method, builds upon our previous method [22], in which the specific problem of LbD was tackled. The advancements of this work, as compared to our previous work, are the following:

- The Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) is utilized for estimating the observed state of the system, which ensures optimal data fusion, as opposed to [22] in a weighted mean was utilized.
- The optimization problem is solved before the repetition of the event, i.e. we seek for the global overall optimum sensor pose and UKF parameters through simulations, as compared to [22] in which the problem was solved in realtime yielding a near-optimal (sub-optimal) solution.

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II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND OBJECTIVE

Let us consider a Repetitive Dynamic Event (RDE), such as the repetitive execution of a physical experiment. Further, consider the availability of a sensor, e.g. a camera, that is able to alter its pose (position and orientation) in order to efficiently gain information. Let $\{S\}$ be the frame of the sensor, and $\mathbf{p}_s \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_s \in SO(3)$ be the position and orientation (in a rotation matrix form) of $\{S\}$ respectively. Without loss of generality, we assume that the RDE is associated with a Point Of Interest (POI)¹. Let $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the coordinates of the POI in Cartesian space. Further, let $\mathbf{x}(t) \triangleq [\mathbf{p}^\top(t) \ \dot{\mathbf{p}}^\top(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^6$ be the state of the system, considering that the evolution of the system can be characterized by a second order differential equation. The RDE is considered to be modelled by an autonomous time-invariant dynamical system of the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}} &= \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{a}), \quad \mathbf{x}(0) = \mathbf{x}_0, \\ \mathbf{y} &= \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) \triangleq [\mathbf{I}_3 \quad \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3}] \mathbf{x}, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represents the measured output, which reflects the position of the POI, \mathbf{I}_n is the $n \times n$ identity matrix, $\mathbf{x}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the initial state of the system, $\mathbf{0}_{n \times n}$ the $n \times n$ zero matrix, $\mathbf{f}(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^6 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^6$ a non-linear (in general) mapping and $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ the parameters of the dynamical system that encode the dynamics of the system, with $m \in \mathbb{N}$ being their quantity. Given that the measurement gathered from the sensor yields after a sampling procedure in time, we consider a discrete time. The time-discretized system, incorporating the uncertainty of both modelling and measurement, is then given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_k &= \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}; \mathbf{a}) + \mathbf{q}_{k-1}, \\ \mathbf{y}_k &= \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}) + \mathbf{v}_k, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}; \mathbf{a}) \triangleq \mathbf{x}_{k-1} + \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}; \mathbf{a})dt$, $\mathbf{q}_k \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the process noise (modelling error) and $\mathbf{v}_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the measurement noise, with $dt \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ being the discretization time interval and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ being the discrete time index. Both \mathbf{q} and \mathbf{v} are considered to be random variables with known normal distributions, i.e. $\mathbf{q} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}_6, \mathbf{Q})$ and $\mathbf{v} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}_3, \mathbf{\Sigma})$, with $\mathbf{Q} \in S_{++}^6$ and $\mathbf{\Sigma} \in S_{++}^3$ being the variance-covariance matrices of the process and measurement noise respectively, and S_{++}^n denoting the set of $n \times n$ positive definite matrices. We assume that $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is a variable of the pose of the sensor as well as the position of the POI. i.e. $\mathbf{\Sigma}(\mathbf{p}_s, \mathbf{R}_s, \mathbf{y})$, which is reasonable for a wide range of sensors and task cases. One related example is the case of identifying the position of a POI with an RGB-D camera, where the uncertainty is relatively higher for the depth provided by the sensor, due to erroneous depth estimation, which is propagated to the whole position estimate using the back-projection mapping.

Our aim is to optimally estimate the state of the system in order to use it for possibly updating the considered model of the RDE. In other words, our aim is to estimate \mathbf{x}_k , in each repetition of the RDE, based on the available $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}; \mathbf{a})$

that currently approximates/models the system, which is probabilistically characterized by \mathbf{Q} and the measurement \mathbf{y}_k , which is probabilistically characterized by $\mathbf{\Sigma}$. To this aim, we employ the notion of Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) [23], which does not involve the analytic computation of the Jacobian of the system, in the expense of introducing a number of parameters that needs to be tuned. Given the difficulty involved in the tuning of the parameters and the fact that $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is considered to be a function of the pose of the sensor, the contribution of the proposed solution is that it automatically seeks for the optimal parameters of the UKF, as well as the optimal pose of the sensor (which in turn affects $\mathbf{\Sigma}$), in order to minimize the total uncertainty of the estimate that will be provided by the UKF during the next repetition of the event. Notice that the pose of the sensor is considered to be static during a single repetition of the event.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

A. Preliminaries on the Unscented Kalman Filtering

The Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) belongs to the "family" of Non-Linear Kalman Filters and it is used for estimating/predicting the state of nonlinear systems. For handling the non-linearity of a system, most non-linear Kalman filters linearize the system at each time instance, and then utilize the basic Kalman filtering idea, which constitutes of fusing the prediction provided by the known dynamical system with the measurement, according to the known covariance of each one of them respectively. For linearizing the system, UKF builds upon the fact that statistics-based numerical approximation of the derivatives, and specifically of the Jacobian of $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$, is easier to perform and more generic than the analytic one.

Let $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ and $\mathbf{P}_{k,k} \in S_{++}^6$ be the state estimate provided by UKF and its covariance matrix respectively, at the k -th time instance. The core idea of Kalman filtering generally, is that the total estimate, i.e. $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k}$, arises after two stages, the "Prediction" stage and the "Update" stage. The novelty in UKF is that the estimation depends on the state distribution which is represented using a minimal set of carefully chosen sample points, the so-called "sigma-points". At the prediction stage, sigma-points are propagated/transformed through a mathematical expression which is called Unscented Transform (UT). For the needs of this paper, the Eric A. Wan and Rudolph van der Merwe approach for $M = 2N + 1$ sigma points selection of the UT is used; where $N \in \mathbb{N}$ is the number of state variables, which in our case is $N = 6$. According to this approach, the i -th sigma-point, denoted as $\mathcal{X}_{k,k}^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^N$, is selected based on the following equation, at each step k :

$$\mathcal{X}_{k,k}^{(i)} = \begin{cases} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k}, & \text{for } i = 1 \\ \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k} + \left(\sqrt{(N + \lambda) \mathbf{P}_{k,k}} \right)_i, & \text{for } i \in [2, N + 1] \\ \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k} - \left(\sqrt{(N + \lambda) \mathbf{P}_{k,k}} \right)_i, & \text{for } i \in [N + 2, M] \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ a constant, whose selection will be given later, and $\left(\sqrt{(N + \lambda) \mathbf{P}_{k,k}} \right)_i$ denotes the i -th column of $\sqrt{(N + \lambda) \mathbf{P}_{k,k}} \in S_{++}^N$. The latter square root can be

¹The extension for incorporating multiple POIs is straight forward.

calculated using the Cholesky decomposition. Taking into consideration the autonomous time-invariant dynamic model, given in (2), the intermediate estimate of the prediction stage and its associated covariance matrix are calculated to be the following:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1} = \hat{\mathcal{X}}_k \mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^N \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{k,k-1} = \tilde{\mathcal{X}}_k \mathbf{W} \tilde{\mathcal{X}}_k^\top + \mathbf{Q}_k \in S_{++}^N \quad (5)$$

where

$$\hat{\mathcal{X}}_k \triangleq \left[\mathbf{f} \left(\mathcal{X}_{k-1,k-1}^{(1)} \right) \dots \mathbf{f} \left(\mathcal{X}_{k-1,k-1}^{(M)} \right) \right] \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}, \quad (6)$$

\mathbf{Q}_k the value of process covariance at k , $\tilde{\mathcal{X}}_k \triangleq \hat{\mathcal{X}}_k - \mathbf{1}_M \otimes \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}$ and $\mathbf{w} = \left[\frac{\lambda}{N+\lambda} \quad \frac{1}{2(N+\lambda)} \quad \dots \quad \frac{1}{2(N+\lambda)} \right]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^M$, $\mathbf{W} = \text{diag} \left(\frac{\lambda}{N+\lambda} + (1 - \alpha^2) + \beta, \frac{1}{2(N+\lambda)} \mathbf{I}_{2N} \right) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}$, with $\alpha \in (0, 1], \beta \in (0, \bar{\beta}]$ being tunable parameters, " \otimes " denoting the Kronecker product and $\mathbf{1}_M \in \mathbb{R}^M$ the all-ones vector, i.e. $\mathbf{1}_M^\top \otimes \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1} = [\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1} \quad \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1} \quad \dots \quad \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1}]$ with $\bar{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ being a preselected upper bound for β . Given a specific selection of α, λ is defined as $\lambda = (\alpha^2 - 1)N$.

Let $\mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the measurement at the k -th step. In the update stage, the measurement is taken into account for the final calculation of the state estimate, denoted with $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ and the total estimation covariance matrix, denoted with $\mathbf{P}_{k,k} \in S_{++}^N$, at each time step, as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1} + \mathbf{K}_k (\mathbf{y}_k - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_k), \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{k,k} = \mathbf{P}_{k,k-1} - \mathbf{K}_k \mathbf{P}_{y,k} \mathbf{K}_k^\top, \quad (8)$$

where

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_k \triangleq \mathbf{Y}_k \mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_k \triangleq \mathbf{P}_{xy,k} \mathbf{P}_{y,k}^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}, \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{Y}_k \triangleq \left[\mathbf{g} \left((\hat{\mathcal{X}}_k)_1 \right) \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{g} \left((\hat{\mathcal{X}}_k)_M \right) \right], \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{y,k} \triangleq \mathbf{A} \mathbf{W} \mathbf{A}^\top + \Sigma(\mathbf{p}_s, \mathbf{R}_s, \mathbf{y}_k) \in S_{++}^N, \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{xy,k} \triangleq \tilde{\mathcal{X}}_k \mathbf{W} \mathbf{A}^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}, \quad (13)$$

with $\mathbf{A} \triangleq \mathbf{Y}_k - \mathbf{1}_M^\top \otimes \hat{\mathbf{y}}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}$.

B. Optimization problem formulation and solution

Notice that as the sensor is considered to be able to change its pose, both \mathbf{p}_s and \mathbf{R}_s are considered to be parameters that can be pre-selected to improve the estimation. Let $\mathbf{p}_c \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the Center of the Scene (CoS), which is assumed to be predefined and $d_s \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ be the nominal sensing distance of the sensor, e.g. for the RGB-D cameras d_s should be selected within the range in which the distance estimation is available. Based on \mathbf{p}_c and d_s , we parameterize the pose of the sensor, i.e. $\mathbf{p}_s, \mathbf{R}_s$, using the angles $\theta \in [0, 2\pi], \phi \in [0, \pi]$ of the polar coordinates of the position of the sensor. For considering a hemisphere instead of a sphere, e.g. in cases in which the event is evolved above a supporting surface, one could consider the range of ϕ to be $[0, \frac{\pi}{2}]$. More specifically, we define an allowable sphere around \mathbf{p}_c for the position of the sensor, as shown in Fig.1, while for the orientation,

Fig. 1: The concept of finding the optimal pose of the sensor. The dotted ellipses represent the covariance of the uncertainty of the sensor.

the parameterization corresponds to the poses in which the sensor's z -axis (which is considered to be the axis along the sensor's direction) is always pointing towards \mathbf{p}_c . Given the above, an example of the exact parameterization of the pose is provided by the following expressions:

$$\mathbf{p}_s(\theta, \phi) = \mathbf{p}_c + d_s [c(\phi) \quad s(\phi)c(\theta) \quad s(\phi)s(\theta)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3, \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_s(\theta, \phi) = [\mathbf{x}_s \quad \tilde{\mathbf{p}} \times \mathbf{x}_s \quad \tilde{\mathbf{p}}] \in SO(3), \quad (15)$$

where $c(\cdot) \equiv \cos(\cdot), s(\cdot) \equiv \sin(\cdot), \tilde{\mathbf{p}} \triangleq \frac{\mathbf{p}_c - \mathbf{p}_s(\theta, \phi)}{\|\mathbf{p}_c - \mathbf{p}_s(\theta, \phi)\|} \in \mathbb{S}^2$ and $\mathbf{x}_s(\theta, \phi) \triangleq \frac{[0 \ 0 \ 1]^\top \times \tilde{\mathbf{p}}(\theta, \phi)}{\|[0 \ 0 \ 1]^\top \times \tilde{\mathbf{p}}(\theta, \phi)\|}$, with " \times " denoting the cross product and " \mathbb{S}^2 " the unit sphere in \mathbb{R}^3 . Based on the above the covariance matrix reflecting the uncertainty of the measurement, i.e. Σ , becomes a function of θ, ϕ .

Remark 1. Notice that it is straight forward to involve any other smooth 2-dof allowable manifold, instead of (14), (15), based on the task requirements or sensor specifications.

Let $\xi \triangleq [\alpha \ \beta \ \theta \ \phi]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^4$ be the vector of parameters that can be tuned for adjusting the quality of the state estimation through UKF. Further, let $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{P}_{k,k})$ be the ellipsoid of the covariance matrix $\mathbf{P}_{k,k}$, where $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{B}) \triangleq \{\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^N : \mathbf{z}^\top \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{z} = 1\}$, for any $\mathbf{B} \in S_{++}^N$. The volume of $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{P}_{k,k})$ is proportional to $\det(\mathbf{P}_{k,k})$. Our goal is to find the optimal set of parameters, denoted with ξ^* , that minimizes the uncertainty of the state estimation trough UKF, reflected by $\det(\mathbf{P}_{k,k})$. As $\mathbf{P}_{k,k}$ is variable in time (i.e. at each k), we are aiming towards solving the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi^* &= \arg \min_{\xi} \sum_{k=1}^{\bar{k}} \det(\mathbf{P}_{k,k}) dt, \\ \text{s. t. } & \alpha \in (0, 1], \beta \in (0, \bar{\beta}], \\ & \theta \in [0, 2\pi], \phi \in [0, \pi], \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $\bar{k} \in \mathbb{N}$ is the duration of the event in discrete time.

As our aim is to find the optimum set of parameters, i.e. ξ^* , before the start of the observation of the repetition of the RDE, we propose the offline solution of (16). To this aim, in order to get the value of $\sum_{k=1}^{\bar{k}} \det(\mathbf{P}_{k,k}) dt$ for a specific ξ ,

we simulate the observation iteration for the given parameter set by adding an artificial process noise, i.e. \mathbf{q}_k , based on the covariance matrix \mathbf{Q}_k , to the simulated evolution of the current model. Furthermore, as the actual ground-truth evolution is not known, the last corrective term of (7) is omitted, which however does not heavily affect the nature of $\mathbf{P}_{k,k}$, on which we focus in this part. For solving the optimization problem, the Covariance matrix adaptation evolution strategy (CMA-ES) is selected, in which the exploration is dictated by a covariance matrix, updated based on the confidence of the solution. The complete function for calculating the cost utilized as the core for CMA-ES, i.e. $\sum_{k=1}^{\bar{k}} \det(\mathbf{P}_{k,k}) dt$, is provided in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Calculation of cost function for a specific ξ

```

1: Input:  $\xi$ 
2: Known:  $\Sigma(\mathbf{p}_s, \mathbf{R}_s, \mathbf{y}_k), \mathbf{Q}_k, dt, \mathbf{x}_0, \bar{k}$ 
3: Initialize  $\mathbf{x}_0$  and  $\mathbf{P}_{0,0} = \mathbf{Q}_0$ 
4: for  $k \in [1, \bar{k}]$  do ▷ Simulation loop
5:   Compute  $\mathcal{X}_{k,k}^{(i)}, \forall i = 1, \dots, 2N + 1$  from (3)
6:   Generate artificial  $\mathbf{q} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}_N, \mathbf{Q}_k)$ 
7:   Compute  $\hat{\mathcal{X}}_k$  from (6) and (2)
8:   Compute  $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1}$  and  $\mathbf{P}_{k,k-1}$  from (4) and (5)
9:   Calculate (9)-(13)
10:  Approximate  $\mathbf{y}_k$ , by setting  $\mathbf{y}_k = \hat{\mathbf{y}}_k$ 
11:  Compute  $\Sigma(\mathbf{p}_s, \mathbf{R}_s, \mathbf{y}_k)$  for  $\xi$ 
12:  Compute  $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k}$  from (7)
13:  Compute  $\mathbf{P}_{k,k}$  from (8)
14:  Store  $\det(\mathbf{P}_{k,k})$ 
15: end for
16: Output:  $\sum_1^{\bar{k}} \det(\mathbf{P}_{k,k}) dt$ 

```

IV. SIMULATION STUDY

For evaluating the robustness of the proposed method given different initial conditions, we conduct numerical simulations in Python and Matlab (the code is provided in the GitHub repository of the experiments), considering the case of estimating the state of a spherical object, having a mass of $m = 1\text{kg}$, rolling within a spherical constraint (radius equal to $L = 1\text{m}$), considering a viscous friction of $b = 0.04\text{Ns/m}$. Towards this direction, for the ground-truth dynamical system we consider: $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_1)\mathbf{x}_2 \\ \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_1) \left(\mathbf{g}_r - \frac{b}{m}\mathbf{x}_2 \right) \end{bmatrix}$, where $\mathbf{x}_1 \triangleq \mathbf{p}$, $\mathbf{g}_r \triangleq [0 \ 0 \ -g]^\top$ is the gravity vector and $\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_1) \triangleq \mathbf{I}_3 - \frac{(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{p}_c)(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{p}_c)^\top}{\|\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{p}_c\|^2}$ is the tangential to the sphere projection matrix, while \mathbf{p}_c is selected to be at the center of the sphere of motion. For the simulations, a hemisphere having a radius of $d_c = 5\text{m}$ is considered as the set of allowable positions of the camera, while the process noise is assumed to be characterized by $\mathbf{Q}_k = \text{diag}(2, 0.1, 0.1, 10, 1, 1) \times 10^{-2}, \forall k = 1, \dots, \bar{k}$, reflecting the case in which the modelling mainly involves an error along the x -axis. The sensor sampling period is considered to be $dt = 0.033\text{s}$, corresponding to a camera sensor set to capture 30 fps. The sensor's uncertainty is set

to $\Sigma = \mathbf{R}_s \text{diag}(0.01, 0.01, 0.2) \mathbf{R}_s^\top$, mimicking an RGB-D camera having a relatively larger uncertainty along the z -axis of $\{S\}$. The values of Σ are not tuned, but predefined reflecting standard deviation of the error equal to 10cm and 44cm, along the $x - y$ axes and z -axis (depth) of the camera respectively. Furthermore, we define a field of view, based on real RGB-D intrinsic parameters, and we set the uncertainty to a maximum value when the POI is not visible, i.e. if \mathbf{p} is not within the field of view, then $\Sigma = 5000\mathbf{I}_3$.

Figure 2 shows the resulted optimized poses (red stars) starting from 49 different initial poses (yellow points) of the sensors, after 80 iterations of the CMA-ES optimization algorithm, considering (16). The initial values of α and β are set to 0.1 and 1 respectively, while the upper bound of β is set to $\bar{\beta} = 5$. Notice, in Fig. 2, the general trend of the optimal poses to align the maximum uncertainty of the camera (i.e. z -axis of the camera) to the minimum uncertainty of the process noise (which is along the $y - z$ plane of the inertial frame). However, the optimal pose is also shaped by other UKF aspects (such as the distribution of the sigma points), and this is why the resulted poses are also seen to be gather in two regions (symmetrically close to the y -axis, which is the main direction of the velocity of POI). In Fig. 3 the estimate provided by the UKF is depicted for the 49th (last) case with the initial parameters being $\xi_0 = [0.1 \ 1 \ 1.047 \ 5.026]^\top$ and the optimal ones being found at $\xi^* = [0.98 \ 0.001 \ 0.95 \ 3.056]^\top$. In Fig. 3, both the results of the arbitrary initial selected non-optimal parameters ξ_0 and the optimal, ξ^* , are presented for comparison, alongside with the corresponding sensor measurements and the ground-truth position. Both the process and the measurement noises are generated using the corresponding normal distribution, i.e. \mathbf{Q} and Σ respectively. Notice the improvement of the estimation achieved (approximately 2.2 times smaller mean estimation error) after moving the camera to the optimal pose and using the parameters found by the proposed method.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

For validating the proposed method, experiments are conducted using a ZED 2 RGB-D camera, attached to the tip of a UR10e robot, as shown in Fig.4. A video recording of the experiments can be found in the following link: <https://youtube.com/shorts/JwgLR7wDzdg>. The task involves the estimation of the state (position and velocity) of a swinging pole, i.e. a pendulum. For detecting the tip of the pole a predetermined April-tag (<https://github.com/AprilRobotics/apriltag>) is utilized, as the detection of specific characteristics/features is outside of the focus of the paper. As the center of the scene (i.e. the center of the sphere of allowable poses), an arbitrary point is selected, close to the pendulum's evolution, namely $\mathbf{p}_c = [0.9 \ 0.28 \ 0.538]^\top\text{m}$, while the allowable sphere is selected to have a radius of $d_c = 0.5\text{m}$, being within the range in which ZED 2 can yield a depth estimate. The pivot point, as well as the exact length of the pole are considered to be parameters of the already modelled dynamical system that are however characterized by an uncertainty. Given the above, the process uncertainty,

Fig. 2: Optimization results for 49 different initial poses of the sensor (yellow dot). The z -axis are always pointing towards the center of the hemisphere.

is considered to be the following:

$$\mathbf{Q}_k = \text{diag}(\mathbf{U} \text{diag}(0.02^2, 0.02^2, 0.1^2) \mathbf{U}^\top, 0.01^2 \mathbf{I}_3), \quad (17)$$

where $\mathbf{U} \in SO(3)$ defines an orthonormal basis having its third column (z -axis) aligned to the estimated direction of the pole (based on the tip and the pivot point). The measurement uncertainty is considered to be similar to that of the simulations, as depth estimation (z -axis of the camera) is characterized by relatively higher uncertainty, adding also a term which is proportional to the April-tags visible area, namely: $\Sigma = (1 + \phi) \mathbf{R}_s \text{diag}(0.002, 0.002, 0.02)^2 \mathbf{R}_s^\top$ (in the considered allowable sphere expression, the higher the ϕ , the smaller the visible area of AprilTag from the camera). Note that when a "NaN", ∞ or $-\infty$ depth estimate is provided by the camera, the algorithm considers the minimum value, which is 0.45m.

The ranges of parameters α, β are set to be similar to the simulations, while the ranges of ϕ and θ are selected to be $[0, \pi/3]$ and $[\pi/2, 7\pi/6]$ respectively, based on the workspace of the robot. To move the robot from one pose to another, a first order Closed Loop Inverse Kinematics (CLIK) algorithm is utilized, sending velocity commands every 2ms to the robot. The whole method is implemented using an external PC that communicates with the robot through a point-to-point ethernet connection, while the code, written in Python, is accessible through GitHub².

The initial parameters for the optimization algorithm, is considered to be $\xi_0 = [0.5 \ 0.2 \ \pi/3 \ \pi/2]^\top$. Figure 5 shows the path estimated through UKF, comparing the cases of both the initial (without optimization) and the optimal pose and parameters found by the proposed method. These are found

Fig. 3: Comparison of estimation $\mathbf{H}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k}$ with and without optimized parameters. The norm of the estimation error is depicted in the last sub-plot. Dashed lines: The measured position of the POI, solid colored lines: the estimate for not optimized UKF parameters (blue), and for the optimized ones (red).

Fig. 4: Experiment using UR10e and ZED 2 as an eye-in-hand.

to be $\xi^* = [0.994 \ 0.386 \ 0.094 \ 1.148]^\top$ (both poses are provided in Fig. 4). Figure 6 depicts the estimated radius of curvature, $\hat{r} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, in each case, which ideally should remain constant. The standard deviation of \hat{r} is computed $\text{std}(\hat{r}) = 1.2\text{mm}$ with the proposed optimized estimation and $\text{std}(\hat{r}) = 7.3\text{mm}$ with the non-optimized one, i.e. more than six times higher. Through Fig. 5 and 6 one can notice the significant improvement, in terms of the quality, noise and smoothness in the estimates, achieved when observing the scene from the optimal pose and using the parameters provided by the proposed method. Further, notice the spikes occurred when the position of the POI is perceived from the

²<https://github.com/CSRL-HMU/ECC.OPTIMIZED.NBV.git>

arbitrary selected pose of the sensor, due to the small visible area of the AprilTag.

Fig. 5: Estimated position of the AprilTag, with and without using the optimal found parameters and pose. Black solid line: UKF estimate, Red dashed line: raw measurement from the camera.

Fig. 6: Estimated radius of curvature.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In the context of estimating the state of a Repetitive Dynamic Event through observation, and considering the availability of an active sensor, this work proposes a method for finding the Next Best View and optimal parameters of the state estimation through UKF. The method assumes that the sensor can alter its pose (i.e. it is actuated) through a mechanism and that the measurement uncertainty is a function of the pose (position and orientation) of the sensor in Cartesian space. The proposed method is evaluated through simulations and experiments using a ZED 2 RGB-D camera attached to the tip of a UR10e robot. The results show the improvement achieved, in terms of state estimation, when using the found optimal pose and parameters, as well as the robustness of the optimal seeking mechanism that uses the proposed cost function.

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A.4 - LAIF: Learning by demonstration through Active Incremental data Fusion of task observations *(Accepted at the 2025 IEEE International Conference on Imaging Systems and Techniques (IEEE IST 2025), Strasbourg, France)*

LAlF: Learning by demonstration through Active Incremental data Fusion of task observations

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Abstract—As William Arthur Ward once said: "Curiosity is the wick in the candle of learning". In this work, inspired by the curiosity that drives human beings, we propose an active perception framework aiming towards the incremental learning through visual observations of multiple demonstrations, performed by a human. The proposed framework, considers an active observer, i.e. a sensor with the ability to move in Cartesian space, which acts in order to maximize the information gathered towards the modelling of the observed motion. For the the encoding of the human action, a Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMP) model is utilized. In the core of the method, a Kalman-filter-inspired data fusion mechanism is employed that exploits the knowledge of the trained DMP model, and accounts for the uncertainty of the current knowledge and the measurement uncertainty, in an iterative manner. The proposed method is tested using a UR5e robotic manipulator with an eye-in-hand ZED 2 camera in two different scenarios, involving the motion of the human hand along a curve, considering the existence of occlusions within the field of view of the camera, as well as an-occlusion-free case. The proposed method is theoretically proven to minimize the uncertainty in each repetition and its performance is demonstrated through the results of the experimental evaluation.

Index Terms—Active Vision, Data fusion, Imitation Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Learning by demonstration (LbD) has gained the researchers' attention worldwide [1], as, in contrast to the traditional explicit programming that is commonly used in industry, it provides an intuitive means for robot programming. According to LbD, the robot is able to learn a kinematic behavior based on a set of demonstrated motions that can be gathered from any perceptual system, e.g. through visual observations [2], [3], or from proprioception [4], [5], i.e. by the robot's own internal sensors. Although LbD through visual observations is widely investigated in current literature, mainly passive observations are considered. In other words, most of the works assume a passive observer that does not possess the ability of moving in space for maximizing the information

gathered. That makes the learning procedure prone to the uncertainty involved in the sensor measurement, which may occur, among others, due to possible occlusions, measurement noise or in general erroneous position estimation (e.g. error in depth estimation).

Most LbD frameworks in literature utilize Dynamical Systems (DS) for encoding the characteristics of the kinematic behavior. From a modelling perspective, LbD can be seen as the problem of finding the parameters of the dynamical system that yield a kinematic behavior which optimally mimics the demonstration dataset, given the same initial conditions. Dynamical systems, as encoding and motion generation mechanisms, provide generalization capabilities, as well as the ability to on-line adapt to dynamic changes. The most common DSs utilized in LbD, in the literature, are the Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs) [6] and the Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) [7].

Data Fusion aims towards the optimal exploitation of multiple data sources for yielding accurate and reliable information about a perceived value. Kalman filtering, introduced in early 60s by Rudolf E. Kálmán [8], and its more recent variants, namely the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) and the Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) [9], are considered to be the most commonly utilized data fusion methods for estimating the state of a system, based on an already known dynamic model of the system and considering a measurement procedure. The uncertainty involved in both the modelling and the measurement are considered to have known statistical characteristics, i.e. a known covariance. The state estimation is essentially performed by fusing the prediction based on the model, with the measured output of the system. Although EKF, UKF or similar data fusion methods were previously combined with DS-based motion generation mechanisms, such as in [10] that aims towards achieving an effective human-robot collaborative object transfer, they were not utilized previously for tackling the problem of active perception for LbD.

The notion of Active Perception was introduced by Aloimonos *et al.* [11], which involves an active observer able of acting in order to maximize the amount of information gathered while perceiving a phenomenon, e.g. a robot with an eye-in-hand camera [3], [12]. Active Perception is widely studied in literature, including industrial [13], [14] and agricultural applications [12], [15], as well as in manipulation [16]. However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, its use to minimize the uncertainty aiming towards increasing the performance of LbD, is not considered previously, given

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the availability of an active observer. Furthermore, the use of Active Perception for tackling the problem of LbD was only considered in [3], in which however the learning was not performed incrementally, thus requiring high memory capacity for storing the data of each repetition, and no occlusions of the point of interest were considered.

In this work, we propose a curiosity-driven LbD methodology, which is based on active observations of recurring demonstrations of the same task. The proposed method considers an active observer (i.e. an observer that can change its position and orientation in Cartesian space), employs a Kalman-filter-like data fusion mechanism for the estimation of the observed system's state and utilizes Dynamic Movement Primitives for the modelling of it in each repetition. The aim of the active observer is to optimally move in order to minimize the uncertainty of the estimate provided by the data fusion mechanism, in real-time, in each iteration, aiming to the optimal encoding/modelling of the observed action. Towards this direction, a control signal is proposed that is able to move the sensor in order to optimally perceive the position of the point of interest.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND OBJECTIVE

Let us consider a Point Of Interest (POI), e.g. human fingertip, whose motion (position in time) is required to be encoded/modelled by the system during the execution of the task. We consider the availability of recurring demonstrations of the same task, e.g. multiple repetitions. Let $\mathbf{p}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the position of the POI with respect to the inertial frame $\{0\}$. Further, consider a sensor (or perception system), e.g. camera, which is attached to a mechanism able of moving in Cartesian space. Let $\{P\}$ be the frame of the sensor and $\mathbf{v}_p \triangleq [\dot{\mathbf{p}}_p^\top \ \omega_p^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^6$ its generalized velocity with respect to $\{0\}$, with $\mathbf{p}_p \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being its position with respect to $\{0\}$ and $\omega_p \in \mathbb{R}^3$ its angular velocity. We consider the case in which one can command the value of $\mathbf{v}_p(t)$ in real-time, while a low-level control scheme is responsible of accurately tracking it¹. Let $\hat{\mathbf{p}} = \mathbf{p} + \varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the measured (by the sensor) position of the POI with respect to $\{0\}$, which is assumed to involve a measurement noise/error $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^3$. The measurement noise is considered to be a random variable having a normal probability distribution, i.e. $\varepsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(\hat{\mathbf{p}}, \Sigma)$, where $\Sigma \in S_{++}^3$ is the variance-covariance matrix of ε with respect to $\{0\}$, with S_{++}^N being the set of $N \times N$ positive definite matrices. The covariance matrix is assumed to be a known function of the orientation of the sensor and the position of the POI, being characterized by the following ellipsoid surface: $\mathcal{S}(\Sigma) \triangleq \{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3 : \mathbf{y}^\top \Sigma^{-1} \mathbf{y} = 1\}$. Let the pose of the sensor be $\mathbf{z}_p \triangleq [\mathbf{p}_p^\top \ \mathbf{q}_p^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{S}^3$ with $\mathbf{q}_p \in \mathbb{S}^3$ being the orientation of $\{P\}$ with respect to $\{0\}$ in a unit quaternion form, with $\mathbb{S}^3 \subset \mathbb{R}^4$ being the set of unit vectors in \mathbb{R}^4 .

Our aim is to design a framework able of acquiring and exploiting information about a recurring phenomenon, namely

¹This is the case in many modern robotic systems, such as mobile robotic vehicles and robotic manipulators.

Fig. 1: The proposed framework at each repetition.

the human demonstration of the same task, by incrementally fusing the data gathered in each repetition with the knowledge accumulated from the previous repetitions. Towards a better definition of the problem, let ${}^i\hat{\mathbf{p}}^*(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the total (accumulative) estimate at the end of the i -th repetition of the phenomenon/demonstration provided by the proposed system and ${}^i\mathbf{P}(t) \in S_{++}^3$ its related covariance. Our objective is to ensure that the volume enclosed by the ellipsoid $\mathcal{S}({}^i\mathbf{P}(t))$, which is proportional to $\det({}^i\mathbf{P}) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, is minimized for all $t \in [0, T]$ in each incremental repetition of the task, i.e. from i to $i + 1$, where $T \in \mathbb{R}_{> 0}$ is the total duration of the task demonstration.

III. THE ACTIVE INCREMENTAL DATA FUSION FRAMEWORK

Let ${}^i\hat{\mathbf{p}} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the measured by the sensor position of the POI during the i -th repetition of the task and ${}^i\hat{\mathbf{p}}^*(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the total estimate provided by the proposed method at the end of the i -th repetition. The main idea of the proposed method is: a) to incrementally (at each repetition of the task demonstration) use the previous model of the task, which is provided by modelling based on the previous estimate, and b) fuse the new incoming measurements with the "prediction" from the model for yielding the new total estimate, and so forth. The total number of repetitions required for a reliable modelling can be assessed by the covariance of the estimate. Towards this direction, the model utilized during the $(i + 1)$ -th repetition, is based and encodes the total estimate of the previous repetitions, i.e. ${}^i\hat{\mathbf{p}}^*(t)$ for all $t \in [0, T]$. For the modelling of the system, the Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMP) model is utilized which is briefly presented below. Moreover, for optimizing the point of view of the sensor, an active perception control signal is proposed that moves the sensor in order to achieve minimization of the uncertainty involved in the data fusion, which is based on both the modelling and the measurement uncertainty. The complete framework is conceptually depicted in Fig. 1.

Remark 1. Note that the data fusion mechanism selected is the covariance-weighted least square solution among the model's prediction and the measurement, which is very close to EKF. The selection of this EKF variant, as compared to the original EKF, is based on extensive comparison through

simulations, which showed that, in our case, it yields better results, due to the fact that original EKF is highly dependent on the initial parameter selection, i.e. the initial uncertainty is propagated to the whole estimate and it is characterized by a transient. Furthermore, this specific variant is significantly computationally lighter, as the on-line calculation of the Jacobian of the DMP is not required.

A. Motion encoding at the end of the $(i-1)$ -th repetition

At the end of the $(i-1)$ -th repetition, the signal ${}^{(i-1)}\hat{\mathbf{p}}^*(t)$ has been calculated for all $t \in [0, T]$. Based on this estimate a DMP model is trained, which is, in turn, used by the data fusion mechanism for the "prediction" during the i -th repetition. The DMP model is a non linear dynamical system of the form: $\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{W})$, where $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) : \mathbb{R}^7 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^7$, $\mathbf{x} \triangleq [\mathbf{x}_1^\top \mathbf{x}_2^\top x_3]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^7$ is the complete state of the system, with $\mathbf{x}_1 \triangleq \mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being the part of the state representing the position of POI (encoding/modelling ${}^{(i-1)}\hat{\mathbf{p}}^*(t)$), $\mathbf{x}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^3$ its velocity and $x_3 \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ is an auxiliary variable, called "phase variable", which replaces time in order for the system to be autonomous. The most important parameters are $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times M}$, which constitutes the "weights" that are adjusted (during the "training" phase) in order for the evolution of the dynamic system to mimic as much as possible the training dataset, with $M \in \mathbb{N}$ being the predefined number of kernels used. More details about the DMP model can be found in [6].

B. State estimation through data fusion at the i -th repetition

The measurement provided by the sensor is fused with the "prediction" from the DMP model by employing a covariance-weighted mean (weighted least square solution) of the data. The rationale behind this selection is to give more importance to the measurement towards the directions in which it is more reliable, as compared to the reliability of the prediction provided by the current modelling, in each iteration, and vice versa. Let $\mathbf{w}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the prediction noise, i.e. the error between the actual position of the POI and the position prediction provided by the DMP model. Given that the DMP model is trained based on the state estimate provided at the end of the previous repetition, it incorporates the uncertainty of this estimate. Therefore, assuming a sufficiently accurate encoding, $\mathbf{w}(t)$ is considered to be a random variable, having a normal distribution with covariance ${}^i\mathbf{Q}_k \in S_{++}^7$, which is equal to the uncertainty of the total estimate after at end of the $i-1$ repetition (i.e. the previous total estimate), or in other words, we set:

$${}^i\mathbf{Q}(t) = {}^{(i-1)}\mathbf{P}(t), \forall t \in [0, T], \quad (1)$$

where ${}^{(i-1)}\mathbf{P}_k \in S_{++}^7$ the covariance of the uncertainty of the total estimate during the $(i-1)$ -th repetition, the calculation of which follows.

Remark 2. Notice that for $i = 1$, i.e. during the first repetition, there is no previous demonstrations and therefore one can consider only the linear part of the DMP with a relatively high uncertainty, e.g. ${}^i\mathbf{Q} = \sigma_0^2 \mathbf{I}_7$, with $\sigma_0 \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ a relatively large value.

For fusing the position measurement provided by the sensor, i.e. $\hat{\mathbf{p}}(t)$, with the position prediction provided by the DMP model, which is represented by $\mathbf{x}_1(t)$, we propose the following covariance weighted mean, as a data fusion mechanism:

$${}^i\hat{\mathbf{p}}^*(t) = ({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1}(t) + \Sigma^{-1}(t))^{-1} ({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1}(t)\mathbf{x}_1(t) + \Sigma^{-1}(t)\hat{\mathbf{p}}(t)). \quad (2)$$

Notice that (2) is essentially the weighted left pseudoinverse solution (weighted least squares) of the following forward relationship: $[\mathbf{x}_1^\top(t) \hat{\mathbf{p}}^\top(t)]^\top = [\mathbf{I}_3 \ \mathbf{I}_3]^\top {}^i\hat{\mathbf{p}}^*(t)$, considering the following weight matrix $\mathbf{W} = \text{diag}({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1}(t), \Sigma^{-1}(t))$, in order to account more for the directions with less uncertainty. The variance-covariance matrix of the total estimate, i.e. ${}^i\mathbf{P}(t) \in S_{++}^3$, can then be calculated by:

$${}^i\mathbf{P}(t) = ({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1}(t) + \Sigma^{-1}(t))^{-1}. \quad (3)$$

Proof of (3):. Given that $\mathbf{x}_1(t)$ is characterized by the modelling uncertainty, having a covariance of ${}^i\mathbf{Q}(t)$, and $\hat{\mathbf{p}}(t)$ by the measurement covariance, i.e. $\Sigma(t)$ and by taking into account (2), one gets:

$$\begin{aligned} {}^i\mathbf{P}(t) &= \text{var}({}^i\hat{\mathbf{p}}^*(t)) = \\ &= ({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \Sigma^{-1})^{-1} {}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} {}^i\mathbf{Q} {}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-\top} ({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \Sigma^{-1})^{-\top} \\ &\quad + ({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \Sigma^{-1}) \Sigma^{-1} \Sigma \Sigma^{-\top} ({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \Sigma^{-1})^{-\top}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Due to the fact that both ${}^i\mathbf{Q}$ and Σ are symmetric positive definite matrices, we have ${}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-\top} = {}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1}$, $\Sigma^{-\top} = \Sigma^{-1}$, $({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \Sigma^{-1})^{-\top} = ({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \Sigma^{-1})^{-1}$ and therefore, (3) yields from (4). \square

Lemma 1. An ellipsoid $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{A})$ is enclosed (or radially surrounded) by another ellipsoid $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{B})$, where $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B} \in S_{++}^3$, if $\mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{y} > \mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{y}$ for all $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3$.

The proof of Lemma 1 is provided in Appendix A.

Theorem 1. The covariance ellipsoid of the total estimate at the i -th repetition, i.e. $\mathcal{S}({}^i\mathbf{P}(t))$, is enclosed (i.e. radially surrounded):

- 1) By the covariance ellipsoid of the $(i-1)$ -th repetition, i.e. $\mathcal{S}({}^{(i-1)}\mathbf{P}(t))$. In other words, the uncertainty of the estimate at each repetition will always be less than the uncertainty at the previous repetition, along any direction.
- 2) By both the covariance ellipsoid of the modelling error, i.e. $\mathcal{S}({}^i\mathbf{Q}(t))$, and the covariance ellipsoid of the measurement, i.e. $\mathcal{S}(\Sigma(t))$. In other words, the uncertainty of the total estimate will always be less than both the measurement and the modelling uncertainty, along any direction.

Proof. Given that ${}^{(i-1)}\mathbf{P}(t) = {}^i\mathbf{Q}(t)$ from (1), $\mathcal{S}({}^{(i-1)}\mathbf{P})$ will constitute the surface for which:

$$\mathbf{y}^\top ({}^{(i-1)}\mathbf{P})^{-1} \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{y}^\top {}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} \mathbf{y} = 1, \mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3, \quad (5)$$

while $\mathcal{S}({}^i\mathbf{P})$ will constitute the surface for which:

$$\mathbf{y}^\top {}^i\mathbf{P}^{-1} \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{y}^\top ({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \Sigma^{-1}) \mathbf{y} = 1, \mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3. \quad (6)$$

Given that both ${}^i\mathbf{Q}$ and Σ are positive definite matrices, the following will hold:

$$\mathbf{y}^\top ({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \Sigma^{-1})\mathbf{y} > \mathbf{y}^\top {}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1}\mathbf{y}. \quad (7)$$

After substituting (5) and (6) into (7), we have:

$$\rho > \mathbf{y}^\top ({}^{i-1})\mathbf{P}^{-1}\mathbf{y}, \quad \rho > \mathbf{y}^\top \Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{y}, \quad \rho > \mathbf{y}^\top {}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1}\mathbf{y}, \quad (8)$$

with $\rho \triangleq \mathbf{y}^\top {}^i\mathbf{P}^{-1}\mathbf{y}$, for all $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3$. Therefore, according to Lemma 1, the first inequality of (8) proves the first part of Theorem 1, while the second and third inequalities prove the second part of it. \square

Remark 3. Assuming that one can rotate the covariance ellipsoid of the measurement, i.e. $\mathcal{S}(\Sigma)$, by rotating the sensor, the second part of Theorem 1 implies that the uncertainty can be optimally minimized by ensuring that $\mathcal{S}(\Sigma)$ is orthogonal to $\mathcal{S}({}^i\mathbf{Q})$, i.e., the major axis of Σ is aligned to the minor axis of ${}^i\mathbf{Q}$ and vice versa (given that they belong to S_{++}^3).

C. Maximizing information through motion

From (3), one can see that ${}^i\mathbf{P}$ depends on $\Sigma(\mathbf{q}_p)$, which in turn depends on the orientation of the sensor, i.e. $\mathbf{q}_p \in \mathbb{S}^3$. Therefore, as our aim is to move the sensor such that the covariance of the uncertainty of the estimate is minimized, the following optimization problem has to be solved in real-time during the observation of the demonstration at the i -th repetition: $\mathcal{J} \triangleq \min_{\mathbf{q}_p \in \mathbb{S}^3} \det({}^i\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{q}_p))$. To this aim, we propose the utilization of the following control signal, as a commanded velocity for the sensor:

$$\mathbf{v}_p \triangleq -k_a \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{p}_c - \mathbf{p}_p) \\ \mathbf{I}_3 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{J}_q^\top(\mathbf{q}_p) \left(\frac{\partial \det({}^i\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{q}_p))}{\partial \mathbf{q}_p} \right)^\top, \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_c \in \mathbb{R}^3$ defines the constant desired center of rotation, or pivot point, of the sensor's movement, which is selected by the designer (it could be defined as the center of the scene), $\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{a}) : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the skew-symmetric matrix mapping of any $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{J}_q(\mathbf{q}_p) \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 3}$ is the matrix that maps the angular velocities to unit quaternion rates, for which it holds $\mathbf{J}_q^\top(\mathbf{q}_p)\mathbf{J}_q(\mathbf{q}_p) = \mathbf{I}_3$. Note that, the columns of $\mathbf{J}_q(\mathbf{q}_p)$ define an orthonormal base on the tangential plane to the unit quaternion sphere and therefore $\mathbf{J}_q(\mathbf{q}_p)\mathbf{J}_q^\top(\mathbf{q}_p)$ is the projection matrix of any vector in \mathbb{R}^4 to the tangential vector space of \mathbb{S}^3 , i.e. the space of feasible unit quaternion rates. Given the above properties, it is easy to show that $\mathbf{J}_q^\top \mathbf{a} = \mathbf{J}_q^\top (\mathbf{J}_q \mathbf{J}_q^\top) \mathbf{a}$, $\forall \mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{R}^4$ and therefore, the last part of (9) constitutes the projection of $\left(\frac{\partial V({}^i\mathbf{P}_k(\mathbf{q}_p))}{\partial \mathbf{q}_p} \right)^\top$ to the feasible, tangential to the unit quaternion sphere, directions. One can find the exact definition of \mathbf{J}_q in Appendix A of [17], denoted by the symbol " \mathbf{J}_Q ". Furthermore, employing the Jacobi's formula, the last term of (9) is calculated as:

$$\frac{\partial \det({}^i\mathbf{P})}{\partial q_j} = \frac{\partial \det({}^i\mathbf{P})}{\partial q_j} = \det({}^i\mathbf{P}) \cdot \text{tr} \left({}^i\mathbf{P}^{-1} \frac{\partial {}^i\mathbf{P}}{\partial q_j} \right), \quad (10)$$

with

$$\frac{\partial {}^i\mathbf{P}}{\partial q_j} = ({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \Sigma^{-1})^{-2} \Sigma^{-2} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial q_j}, \quad (11)$$

where q_j , with $j = 1, \dots, 4$ the elements of $\mathbf{q}_p \in \mathbb{S}^3 \subset \mathbb{R}^4$.

D. The complete framework

Integrating the above components in one single method, as shown in Fig. 1, the proposed solution can minimize the uncertainty involved in the modelling of the task, within a number of iterations. Regarding the memory capacity required, in each iteration, only the trained DMP model weights and the covariance of the estimate have to be stored, i.e. \mathbf{W} and ${}^i\mathbf{P}_k$ for all $k \in [0, k_N]$ respectively, where $k_N \in \mathbb{N}$ the total number of samples gathered, as opposed to [3], in which the learning was not performed incrementally. The Python (real experiments) and Matlab (simulation) implementation of the algorithm can be found in the following link, providing also a pseudocode: <https://github.com/CSRL-HMU/AIF-LbD>. Notice that the computational cost of computing (11) is $O(n^3)$ with $n = 6$, which means that the algorithm is implementable in real-time without high-computation requirements.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

A video of the experimental and simulation evaluations, can be found in this link: <https://youtu.be/ECnM2dK781w>. For the experimental validation, the UR5e robot is utilized, having an in-hand ZED 2 RGB-D camera sensor attached to its tip, while the Point Of Interest is considered to be the index finger of the human. The framework was implemented using Python, while for the forward kinematic and the Jacobian of the robot, the Robotics Toolbox (<https://petercorke.com/toolboxes/robotics-toolbox/>) was utilized. For identifying the human fingers, the pre-trained "Mediapipe Hands" [18] algorithm was utilized in real time, while for identifying any other objects (possibly occluding the field of view), YOLOv8 (<https://docs.ultralytics.com/models/yolov8/>) was employed. The latter detection algorithms were running on a separate (from the control loop) thread, in order to ensure that the control cycle, which was set to 2ms, is not affected. The resolution of the camera was selected to be 1280x720, while its frame rate was set to 60 FPS; however, this rate was reduced by the detection algorithms which were running in real time, therefore yielding a new finger estimate approximately every 71ms. It should be noted that when no depth values were provided by the sensor, i.e. a "NaN" was given, a default preset value was considered for the depth.

The estimated covariance of the uncertainty of the camera sensor was set to $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = 40$ pixels, both on x and y axis of the pixel space, sourcing mainly from the finger-detection accuracy, while the covariance of the depth estimate was set to $\sigma_3 = 0.3\text{m}$. Given that the intrinsic parameters of the camera are provided by the manufacturer, the covariance of the 3-D position estimate, based on the back-projection pinhole relationship of the camera, is given by:

$$\Sigma(\mathbf{q}_p) = 2^\mu \mathbf{R}_p(\mathbf{q}_p) \text{diag} \left(\frac{\sigma_1^2}{f_x^2} (\sigma_3^2 + \hat{p}_{cx}^2), \frac{\sigma_2^2}{f_y^2} (\sigma_3^2 + \hat{p}_{cy}^2), \sigma_3^2 \right) \mathbf{R}_p^\top(\mathbf{q}_p),$$

where $\mu \in \{0, 1\}$ is the binary variable that takes the value "0" when the POI is not occluded and "1" if it is, $f_x, f_y \in \mathbb{R}$

(a) The case of fully visible POI. (b) View of the camera (case involving occlusions of POI)

Fig. 2: The two cases considered for the experimental validation.

the focal lengths of the camera sensor along the x and y axes respectively, and $\hat{p}_{cx}, \hat{p}_{cy} \in \mathbb{R}$ the x and y coordinates of the position estimate of the POI with respect to the camera frame $\{P\}$. Notice that the uncertainty is considered to be doubled when the POI is occluded, due to the multiplication with 2^μ . Furthermore, notice that the ellipsoid's volume is minimum when the point is located at the center of the camera, i.e. when $p_{cx} = p_{cy} = 0$. For the DMP model, we utilized $M = 100$ kernel functions and a linear canonical system. The gain of the proposed method was selected to be $k_a = 5 \cdot 10^4$ when no occlusions were considered in the scene, and $k_a = 3 \cdot 10^4$, when considering occlusions. Notice the relatively large value of the gain, due to the fact that the control signal involves its multiplication by the volume of the ellipsoid, which is relatively small (scale of 10^{-6}).

For the experiments, the human was instructed to follow a predefined path annotated on a table, in order to use it as a ground-truth for the evaluation, as shown in Fig. 2. No information about this path was provided to the proposed framework. For testing the performance of the proposed framework, we consider two cases. The first case involves the observation of the finger's motion without considering any occlusions to the scene (Fig. 2a), while for the second case an obstacle (plastic mock-up fruit) was considered to intercept the view of the POI, during a part of its motion, as shown in Fig. 2b, as seen by the camera. For detecting if an occlusion occurs, we compare the depth of the fingertip's estimate (provided by MediaPipe) to that of the object (identified by YOLOv8), if the finger's position in the pixel space is within the bounding box of the object². Lastly, three repetitions of the task were considered, as during the third repetition, the uncertainty of the estimate was deemed already sufficiently minimized.

In Fig. 3 the paths of the estimated position of the POI are shown, in each repetition i , for both cases: without and with occlusions. The orientation of the camera during its motion can be inferred by the direction of the Σ -ellipsoid, in each case. Notice the noise of the measurement during the first repetition when no occlusions are considered (Fig. 3a), mainly

²Notice that a simplified rationale was employed for this specific aspect, as the focus of the proposed framework is not towards the development of such detection algorithms

due to "NaN-value spikes" in depth estimate, which however are sufficiently rejected by the proposed method after the second repetition of the demonstration (black solid line in Fig. 3b). Further notice the action of the camera during the second observation (from the ellipsoids in Fig. 3b), which aims towards achieving the orthogonality between Σ and iQ . Let us note that the velocity (i.e. its total motion) of the sensor during the third observation was significantly reduced, as the volume of iP was relatively small. This condition can serve as an indication that no further repetitions are required, i.e. that the system has accumulated sufficient knowledge.

In the case in which occlusions are considered, notice the erroneous path segment, at the middle of the motion during the first ($i = 1$) repetition, associated with a relatively larger uncertainty (Fig. 3e), due to the occlusion of the POI by the obstacle. However, notice that due to the high uncertainty considered automatically by the proposed method, during the 2nd repetition (Fig. 3f) this erroneous segment is smoothly "replaced" by the corresponding part of the measurement, which did not involve any occlusions, as the pose of the sensor was automatically optimized by the proposed framework.

Lastly notice the reduction of the uncertainty achieved due to the motion of the sensor, based on the proposed signal, during the second repetition, in both cases, which is reflected by $\det^2 P(t)$, depicted in Fig. 3d and 3h for each case respectively.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

In this work, an active perception Learning by Demonstration framework is proposed, considering the availability of recurring demonstrations of the same task and an active observer (active sensor). The proposed framework combines Kalman-filter-like Data Fusion, Dynamic Movement Primitives and the notion of Active Perception for achieving optimal learning within a couple of repetitions of the task, performed by the human. The experimental results, which consider a robot with an eye-in-hand RGB-D camera and involve occlusions and erroneous depth measurements, demonstrate the minimization of the uncertainty achieved by the proposed method, as well as noise rejection, within a couple of repetitions.

Future research directions involve the extension of the method to incorporate multiple active observers and its application to realistic environments for the modeling of Repetitive Dynamic Events (e.g. recurring fire in critical assets). Regarding the considered hardware, future directions involve the utilization of mobile robots, such as quadruped robots, and different sensor modalities, such as thermal cameras.

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Fig. 3: Path of the incremental estimate and $\det({}^i\mathbf{P}(t))$, in both cases. Cyan dotted line: \hat{p} (measurement), black solid line: ${}^i\hat{p}^*$ (total incremental estimation), green dotted line: $\mathbf{x}_1(t)$, red ellipse: $S({}^i\mathbf{Q})$, blue ellipse: $S(\Sigma)$, black ellipse: $S({}^i\mathbf{P})$, yellow dashed line: $\mathbf{p}_r(t)$ (reference/ground truth position of the POI). Notice that the surface $S({}^1\mathbf{Q}(t))$ (at $i = 1$), is not depicted, as for $i = 1$ it consists of a sphere of a relatively large radius that would distort the presentation.

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APPENDIX A - PROOF OF LEMMA 1

Proof. Let $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{S}^2$ be a unit vector pointing towards an arbitrary direction, where $\mathbb{S}^2 \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ the set of unit vectors in \mathbb{R}^3 . We can show that $S(\mathbf{A})$ is enclosed by $S(\mathbf{B})$, by showing that $a < b$, where $a \in \mathbb{R}_{>0} : (a\mathbf{n})^\top \mathbf{A}^{-1}(a\mathbf{n}) = a^2 \mathbf{n}^\top \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{n} = 1$ and $b \in \mathbb{R}_{>0} : (b\mathbf{n})^\top \mathbf{B}^{-1}(b\mathbf{n}) = b^2 \mathbf{n}^\top \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{n} = 1$, for any direction $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{S}^2$. Notice that a and b represent the length of the linear segments within $S(\mathbf{A})$ and $S(\mathbf{B})$ respectively, along the direction of \mathbf{n} . To this aim, we have $\mathbf{n}^\top \mathbf{A} \mathbf{n} = \frac{1}{a^2}$ and $\mathbf{n}^\top \mathbf{B} \mathbf{n} = \frac{1}{b^2}$. Then $\mathbf{n}^\top \mathbf{A} \mathbf{n} > \mathbf{n}^\top \mathbf{B} \mathbf{n}$ implies $\frac{1}{a^2} > \frac{1}{b^2}$ and consequently $a < b$. \square